

ICS

Instituto de Ciências Sociais da Universidade de Lisboa

consensus

**CONSENSUS
CONFRONTING SOCIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL
SUSTAINABILITY WITH ECONOMIC PRESSURE:
BALANCING TRADE-OFFS BY POLICY DISMANTLING OR
EXPANSION?**

**PORTUGAL
(ENVIRONMENT)**

EQUIPA DE INVESTIGAÇÃO ICS
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Environmental Policy, Part 1: Clean Air Policy

(Emission regulations, air quality standards, definitions of concrete limit values, etc.)

<i>Year</i>	<i>Type of legislation</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Objective</i>	<i>Data supplied</i>
1976	no legislative activity			
1977	no legislative activity			
1978	no legislative activity			
1979	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 57/79	Establishes the limit values for several parameters in the Sines industrial complex and attributes competence to the Sines Area Cabinet to implement them	DL_57_79_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1980	Decreto	Decreto n.º 45/80	Approves, for ratification, the United Nations convention on Long-Distance Transborder Atmospheric Pollution	D_45_80_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1980	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 255/80	Gives the Territorial Planning and Environment Secretariat powers to set concentration limits on surface and over atmospheric pollutant emissions.	DL_255_80_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1980	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 443/80	Determines that the Air Pollution Work Group operates within the framework of the Territorial Planning and Environment Secretariat	DL_443_80_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1980	Decreto	Decreto n.º 106/80	Approves, for ratification, Convention No. 148 relating to Protection of Workers against Occupational Hazards due to Air Pollution	D_106_80_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1981	Portaria	Portaria n.º 508/81	Approves the General Regulation of the Air Management Commissions.	P_508_81_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1981	Despacho Normativo	Despacho Normativo n.º 168/81	Establishes values for total sulphur dioxide and particles in the vicinity in which the Sines Area Cabinet operates	DN_168_81_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1982	Portaria	Portaria n.º 290/82	Approves Portuguese norm NP.1825 (1982, relating to reading atmospheric pollutants levels)	P_290_82_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1982	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 476/82	Promotes lowering the quantity of imported trichlorofluoromethane and dichlorofluoromethane as products or raw material	DL_476_82_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1983	Portaria	Portaria n.º 668/83	Approves Portuguese norm NP-2318 for air quality and determines the level of carbon monoxide released while engines are at idle speed	P_668_83_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1984	Portaria	Portaria n.º 472/84	Establishes new values for lead and octane index	P_472_84_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1985	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 216/85	Lays down norms to structure activities of storing, collecting and burning used oils.	DL_216_85_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1985	Despacho Normativo	Despacho Normativo n.º 110/85	Lays down norms relating to pollutants produced by industrial establishments	DN_110_85_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1986	no legislative activity			
1987	Despacho normativo	Despacho normativo n.º 29/87	Establishes guide values for sulphur dioxide, airborne particles, nitrogen dioxide and limit values for lead	DN_29_87_AIR_Portugal.pdf

1987	Lei	Lei n.º 11/87	Foundations of Environmental Law – General Principles defend measures that ensure air quality	L_11_87__AIR_Portugal.pdf
1987	Portaria	Portaria n.º 427/87	Lays down criteria for homologation of motor vehicles and their components and the dates for its application in Portugal	P_427_87_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1988	Decreto do Governo	Decreto do Governo n.º 5/88	Approves, for adhesion to, the protocol to the 1979 Convention on Long-Distance Transborder Atmospheric Pollution	DG_5_88_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1988	Decreto	Decreto n.º 20/88	Approves, for ratification, the Montreal Protocol on Substances that Deplete the Ozone Layer, as well as the respective Annex A	D_20_88_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1988	Decreto	Decreto n.º 23/88	Approves, for adhesion, the Vienna Convention for the Protection of the Ozone Layer, as well as Annexes I and II	D_23_88_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1988	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 464/88	Applies to Portugal the Community regulation on forest protection against atmospheric pollution	DL_464_88_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1989	Portaria	Portaria n.º 124/89	Lays down measures against the emission of pollutants from diesel engines of wheeled agricultural or forestry tractors	P_124_89_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1989	Portaria	Portaria n.º 125/89	Establishes petrol characteristics, including lead content	P_125_89_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1989	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1009/89	Lays down norms for the homologation of motor vehicles and their components and sets dates for their application in Portugal and updates annexes to the Decree No. 427/87	P_1009_89_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1989	Despacho conjunto	Despacho conjunto (2.ª Série, 26/08/1989)	Sets a working group on the protection of the Ozone layer, specially on matters concerning the production and consumption of CFC's	Hardcopy_DC_26_08_1989_AIR_Portugal
1990	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 352/90	Defines the air quality protection and control system	DL_352_90_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1990	Portaria	Portaria n.º 534/90	Transposes norms about motor vehicles and their components from directives 89/491/CEE, 89/516/CEE, 89/517/CEE and 89/518/CEE	P_534_90_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1990	Portaria	Portaria n.º 725/90	Changes some conditions established in Portaria n.º 1009/89, about motor vehicles and their components, according to directive 88/76/CEE and directive 89/459/CEE	P_725_90_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1991	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 109/91	Lays down air quality norms for nitrogen dioxide in industrial activities	DL_109_91_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1991	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 10/91	Regulates air quality norms for nitrogen dioxide in industrial activities	DR_10_91_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1991	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 195/91	Allows the use of liquefied petrol gas as fuel for motor vehicles and establishes the system for approval of vehicles adapted to use this fuel	DL_195_91_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1992	Portaria	Portaria n.º 240/92	Establishes limit values to emission of certain substances emitted in combustion of oils used in thermal power installations equal or above 3 MW (PCI)	P_240_1992_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1992	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 108/92	Lays down preventive measures to avoid hazards that certain aerosol packaging may cause	DL_108_92_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1992	Decreto	Decreto n.º 39/92	Approves, for ratification, amendments to the Montreal Protocol on Substances that Deplete the Ozone Layer	D_39_92_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1992	Portaria	Portaria n.º 952/92	Approves the regulation of Metrologic Control of Measuring Instruments for Motor Vehicles Exhaust Fumes	P_952_92_AIR_Portugal.pdf

1992	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 259/92	Establishes the system of entities accredited to intervene within the area of environment control	DL_259_92_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1992	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1233/92	Defines the general regulation on air management commissions	P_1233_92_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1993	Portaria	Portaria n.º 22/93	Permits in 1993 the registration of passenger vehicle manufacturers, or legal representatives, of exemption from technical norms relating to exhaust fumes emission	P_22_93_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1993	Portaria	Portaria n.º 267/93	Requires periodic motor vehicle inspection	P_267_93_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1993	Portaria	Portaria n.º 286/93	Sets limit values and guide values with relation to air	P_286_93_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1993	Portaria	Portaria 287-A/93	Requires certain categories of motors to undergo obligatory periodic inspections	P_287A_93_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1993	Aviso	Aviso n.º 88/93	Makes known that the Permanent Representative of Portugal to the United Nations deposited the instrument for ratification of amendments to the Montreal Protocol on Substances that Deplete the Ozone Layer	A_88_1993_AIR_Portugal.doc
1993	Despacho conjunto	Despacho conjunto, de 18-05-1993 (2.ª Série)	Determines the specifications of oils used as fuel	Hardcopy_DC_18_05_1993_AIR_Portugal
1993	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 192/93	Establishes the Meteorological Institute regulations	DL_192_93_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1993	Declaração de Rectificação	Declaração de Rectificação n.º 91/93	Rectifies Decree 286/93, relating to limit values and guide values	DREC_91_93_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1993	Decreto	Decreto n.º 20/93	Approves for ratification the Framework Convention on Climatic Change	D_20_93_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1993	Aviso	Aviso n.º 222/93	Makes known a correction made to Annexes I and II of the Framework Convention on Climatic Change	A_222_93_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1993	Decreto	Decreto n.º 37/93	Approves for ratification the Convention on the Control of Transboundary Movement of Hazardous Waste and their Disposal	D_37_1993_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1994	Portaria	Portaria n.º 53/94	Transposes Directive 93/59/EC relating to measures to take about air pollution due to emissions from motor vehicles	P_53_94_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1994	Aviso	Aviso n.º 129/94	Makes known that Portugal on 21 December 1993 deposited letters of ratification of the Framework Convention on Climatic Change, concluded in New York on 9 May 1992	A_129_94_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1994	Portaria	Portaria n.º 58/94	Alters Annexes I and II of Decree No. 1009/89 of 21 November (establishing an application calendar for Portugal of the technical norms relating to motor vehicles and their components)	P_58_94_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1994	Portaria	Portaria n.º 768/94	Allows manufacturers of motor vehicles and their representatives in 1995 to register end-of-series vehicles as exempt from technical norms relating to exhaust fumes emission	P_768_94_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1994	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1058/94	Sets general limit values for the environment of carbon dioxide, airborne particles. Nitrogen dioxide and monoxide and guide values for the ozone. Alters decree 286/93.	P_1058_94_AIR_Portugal.pdf

1995	Despacho	Despacho n.º 79/95, (II Série, 12-01-1996)	Self-monitoring of industrial emissions into atmosphere through continuous measuring. Approves new technique of sending results to competent authorities (within the terms of Decree-Law No.325/90 of 09-11-1990)	Hardcopy_Desp_79_1995_AIR_Portugal
1995	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 38/95	Approves Environment Policy Plan (PNPA), which includes strategic guidelines for air quality	RCM_38_95__AIR_Portugal.pdf
1996	Portaria	Portaria n.º 623/96	Defines mechanisms for monitoring, the interchange of information, and information for and warnings to the public about ozone pollution. Repeals Decree No.286/93	P_623_96_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1997	Decreto	Decreto n.º 27/97	Approves, for ratification, alterations to the Montreal Protocol on Substances that Deplete the Ozone Layer	D_27_1997_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1997	Despacho	Despacho 73 (II Série, 06-01-1997)	Establishes specifications of the method to measure emissions – asbestos	Hardcopy_Desp_73_1997_AIR_Portugal
1997	Portaria	Portaria n.º 125/97	Relating to limit values of emissions from installations of urban waste incineration. Alters wording of Annex VI of Decree 286/93	P_125_97_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1997	Portaria	Portaria n.º 399/97	Relating to limit values of emissions of large fuel installations. Alters wording of No. 9 of Annex VI of Decree 286/93	P_399_97_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1997	Portaria	Portaria n.º 646/97	Transposes Directive 94/63/EC on emissions of volatile organic compounds	P_646_97_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1997	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 166/97	Transposes Directive 93/76/EC on limits to CO2 emissions	RCM_166_97_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1998	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 72/98	Sets up a Commission on Climatic Change	RCM_72_98_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1998	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 226/98	Determines that competences related to air quality control should be transferred to the General Directorate of Environment	DL_226_98_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1998	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 273/98	Relating to limit values on emissions of hazardous waste incineration installations – transposes the dispositions of Directive 94/67/EC	DL_273_98_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1999	Lei	Lei n.º 20/99	Industrial waste treatment	L_20_99_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1999	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 120/99	Sets up a special control system and environmental inspection of co-incineration	DL_120_99_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1999	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 121/99	Attributes competence in accordance to article 4 of Law No.20/99 to the Independent Scientific Commission set up by Decree-Law No.120/99, and ends suspension of ruling of norms on inspection and sanctioning of constant co-incineration operations of Decree-Law No.273/98	DL_121_99_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1999	Lei	Lei n.º 148/99	First alteration, by parliamentary deliberation, of Decree-Law No. 121/99, of 16 of April, which attributes competence in accordance to article 4 of Law No.20/99 to the Independent Scientific Commission set up by Decree-Law No.120/99, and ends the suspension of the ruling of norms on inspection and sanctioning of constant co-incineration operations of Decree-Law No.273/98	L_148_99_AIR_Portugal.pdf

1999	Lei	Lei n.º 149/99	First alteration, by parliamentary deliberation, of Decree-Law No. 120/99, of 16 April, which set up a special control system and environmental inspection of co-incineration	L_149_99_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1999	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 276/99	Defines the guidelines of air quality management policy	DL_276_99_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1999	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 432/99	Establishes the patterns of emission and homologation processes of motors in non-road mobile machinery	DL_432_99_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1999	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 549/99	Approves the Organic Law of the General Inspectorate of Environment	DL_549_99_AIR_Portugal.pdf
1999	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 554/99	Transposes Directive 96/96/CE changed by 1999/52/CE technical norms relating to roadworthiness tests for motor vehicles and their trailers	DL_554_99_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2000	Lei	Lei n.º 22/2000	First alteration of Law No.20/99, of 15 April (industrial waste treatment)	L_22_2000_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2000	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 69/2000	Approves the legal system of environmental impact assessment, transposing the Directive 85/337/EC to Portuguese regulation with alterations made to Directive 97/11/EC	DL_69_2000_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2000	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 72/2000	Approves the regulation of EC homologation of motor vehicles and trailers, their systems, components and technical units	DL_72_2000_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2000	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 104/2000	Lays down dispositions on technical specifications applicable to petrol and diesel fuels for vehicles equipped with positive-ignition and compression-ignition engines, and transposes Directive 98/70/EC	DL_104_2000_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2000	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 194/2000	Transposes Directive 66/91/EC, relating to integrated pollution prevention and control	DL_194_2000_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2000	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 202/2000	Regulates homologation of vehicles, systems and technical units relating to pollutant emissions and simultaneously transposes to Portuguese regulation Directives 98/69/EC of the European Parliament and Council of 13 October 1998 and 98/77/EC	DL_202_2000_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2000	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 253/2000	Approves regulation of CO2 emissions and fuel consumption of automobiles	DL_253_2000_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2000	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 281/2000	Establishes limits to sulphur content in certain types of petrol-derived fuels	DL_281_2000_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2001	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 26/2001	Alters EC Regulation of homologation of vehicles, systems and technical units relating to pollutant emissions	DL_26_2001_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2001	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 59/2001	Approves Climatic Change Strategy	RCM_59_2001_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2001	Lei	Lei n.º 93/2001	Creates instruments to prevent climatic change and its effects	L_93_2001_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2001	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 154-A/2001	Ends the suspension of the ruling of norms of Decree-Law No.273/98 with regard to co-incineration operations of hazardous industrial waste, including assessment and selection of sites for burning and treating this waste	DL_154-A_2001_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2001	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 242/2001	Transposes Directive 1999/13/EC on volatile organic compounds emissions	DL_242_2001_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2001	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1047/2001	Approves licensing model for economic activities included in Decree-Law No.	P_1047_2001_AIR_Portugal.pdf

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2001	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 290/2001	Establishes limit values to exposure of workers to some chemical agents. Transposes Directive 98/24/EC; and Directives 91/322/EC and 2000/39/EC	DL_290_2001_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2001	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 304/200	Establishes a system of information for the consumer about fuel consumption and CO2 emissions of passenger cars (transposes Directive 1999/94/EC)	DL_304_2001_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 13/2002	Regulates pollutant emissions of engines fuelled by diesel, compressed natural gas or liquefied petroleum gas	DL_13_2002_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto	Decreto n.º 7/2002	Approves the Kyoto Protocol	D_7_2002_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto	Decreto n.º 35/2002	Approves amendments to the 1987 Montreal Protocol on Substances that Deplete the Ozone Layer	D_35_2002_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 107/2002	Transposes Directive 2001/9/EC and Directive 2001/11/EC, which respectively regulate tests to check and control exhaust emissions and compulsory control of vehicles' maximum speed	DL_107_2002_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 111/2002	Fixes limit values for sulphur dioxide, nitrogen dioxide, nitrogen oxides, airborne particles, lead, benzene and carbon monoxide. Defines air quality management regulations applicable to these pollutants	DL_111_2002_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 114/2002	Transposes Directive 2000/25/EC, thereby approving the regulation against the emission of gaseous and particulate pollutants by engines intended to power agricultural or forestry tractors	DL_114_2002_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 119/2002	Aims at ensuring the compliance of the Portuguese Government's obligations with Regulation (EC) 2037/2000, relating to on substances that deplete the ozone layer substances	DL_119_2002_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 150/2002	Alters No.4 of Article 7 of Decree-Law 104/2000	DL_150_2002_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 175/2002	Extinguishes the Independent Scientific Commission of Environmental Control and Inspection of Co-incineration created by Decree-Law No. 120/99, 16 April	DL_175_2002_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 202/2002	Transposes Directive 2001/63/EC, which adapts to technical progress Directive 97/68/EC, relating to the approximation of the laws of Member States relating to measures against the emission of gaseous and particulate pollutants from internal combustion engines to be installed in non-road mobile machinery, thereby altering Decree-Law No. 432/99	DL_202_2002_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 236/2002	Alters regulation on EC homologations of vehicles, systems and technical units relating to pollutant emissions (Transposes Directive 2001/1EC)	DL_236_2002_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 237/2002	Alters the regulation on emissions of engines fuelled by diesel, compressed natural gas or liquefied petrol gas	DL_237_2002_AIR_Portugal.pdf

2003	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 72-D/2003	Transposes Directive 2001/100/EC, and alters the regulation on EC homologations of vehicles, systems and technical units relating to pollutant emissions, approved by Decree-Law No. 202/2000	DL_72-D_2003_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2003	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 178/2003	Establishes the limits of emissions of certain pollutants coming from large combustion plants (nominal potency above 50 MW)	DL_178_2003_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2003	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 193/2003	Sets national emission ceilings for certain atmospheric pollutants to 2010 and 2020 (Transposes Directive 2001/81/EC)	DL_193_2003_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2003	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 8/2003	Approves Regulation for the Licensing of Industrial Activities	DR_8_2003_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2003	Declaração de Rectificação	Declaração de Rectificação n.º 11-B/2003.	Rectifies Decree-Law No. 178/2003, on the limits of emissions of certain pollutants coming from large combustion plants	DREC_11-B_2003_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2003	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 224/2003	Alters Regulation of EC homologations of vehicles, systems and technical units relating to pollutant emissions	DL_224_2003_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2003	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 320/2003	Transposes Directive 2002/3/EC relating to ozone in ambient air	DL_320_2003_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2003	Portaria	Portaria n.º 464/2003	Establishes a new legal regime for industrial activities	P_464_2003_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2003	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1387/2003	Introduces security and control measures relating to the use petrol coke in industry	P_1387_2003_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2003	Despacho conjunto	Despacho conjunto n.º 1083/2003 (2.ª Série)	Determines the setting up of the group work for climatic change and attributes tasks under the Commission on Climate Change	DC_1083_2003_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2004	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 78/2004	Establishes the regime of prevention and control of pollutant emissions into the atmosphere and sets the principles, aims and appropriate instruments to ensure the protection of air resources	DL_78_2004_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2004	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 109/2004	Transposes Directive 2003/27/EC relative to exhaust emissions control of engines and alters Decree-Law No. 554/99	DL_109_2004_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2004	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 132/2004	Alters Decree-Law No.202/2000 and transposes Directive 2003/76/EC relative to emissions from motor vehicles	DL_132_2002_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2004	Decreto	Decreto n.º 20/2004	Approves the Protocol to the 1979 Convention on Long-range Transboundary Air Pollution on Reduction of Acidification, Eutrophication and Tropospheric	D_20_2004_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2004	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 119/2004	Approves the National Climate Change Programme	RCM_119_2004_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2004	Aviso	Aviso n.º 152/2004	Makes known that on 15 April 2004 the Portuguese Government deposited its instrument of acceptance relating to the Stockholm Convention on Persistent Organic Pollutants, signed on 22 May 2001	A_152_2004_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2004	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 233/2004	Determines the trading regime of greenhouse gas emissions permits	DL_233_2004_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2004	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 235/2004	Establishes the introduction and availability of petrol and diesel oil with a maximum sulphur content of 10mg/kg	DL_235_2004_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2004	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 243-A/2004	Alters the trading regime of greenhouse gas emissions permits (Decree-Law 233/2004)	DL_243A_2004_AIR_Portugal.pdf

2005	Portaria	Portaria n.º 118/2005	Sets the Environment Institute fees for issuing greenhouse gas emissions permits and their updates	P_118_2005_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2005	Portaria	Portaria n.º 120/2005	Approves the model of application for a greenhouse gas emissions permit	P_120_2005_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2005	Portaria	Portaria n.º 121/2005	Sets the monitoring guidelines that will be approved by the Environment Institute	P_121_2005_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2005	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 53/2005	Approves the National Plan for issuing emissions permits (PNALE - <i>Plano Nacional de Atribuição de Licenças de Emissão</i>) relating to 2005-2007	RCM_53_2005_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2005	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 59/2005	Approves the monitoring and assessment climate change programme of the National Plan	RCM_59_2005_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2005	Portaria	Portaria n.º 263/2005	Sets new regulations for calculating chimney heights and defines situations in which atmospheric pollutants studies must be carried out to this effect	P_263_2005_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2005	Despacho	Despacho n.º 5936/2005 (2.ª série)	Approval of minutes of the protocol that implements the National Emission Reduction Plan	Desp_5936_2005_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2005	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 68/2005	Sets up the National Inventory System of Source Emissions and Removal by Sinks of Atmospheric Pollutants (SNIERPA - <i>Sistema Nacional de Inventário de Emissões por Fontes e Remoção por Sumidouros de Poluentes Atmosféricos</i>)	RCM_68_2005_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2005	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 85/2005	Establishes the regime for waste incineration and co-incineration in order to prevent or, as far as possible, reduce to a minimum harmful effects on the atmosphere, in particular pollution as a result of emissions into the air, soil and surface and subterranean water	DL_85_2005_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2005	Declaração de Rectificação	Declaração de Rectificação n.º 38/2005	Rectifies Ordinance (<i>Portaria</i>) No. 263/2005, of 17-03-2005	DREC_38_2005_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2005	Declaração de Rectificação	Declaração de Rectificação n.º 44/2005	Rectifies Decree-Law No. 85/2005 on waste incineration and co-incineration and their harmful environmental effects, especially on air quality	DRec_44_2005_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2005	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 152/2005	Regulates maintenance, assistance or recovery, recycling, enhancement and destruction of equipment that contains substances that deplete the ozone layer	DL_152_2005_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2005	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 178/2005	Alters the regulation on carbon dioxide emissions and motor fuel consumption (approved by Decree-Law No. 253/2000) and the regulation of EC homologation of motor vehicles and trailers, their systems, components and technical units (Decree-Law No. 72/2000). Transposes Directive 2004/3/EC	DL_178_2005_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2005	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 184/2005	Alters Decree-Law No. 304/2001 and transposes Directive 2003/73/EC relating to the provision of fuel consumption and carbon dioxide emissions information	DL_184_2005_AIR_Portugal.pdf
2005	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 230/2005	Alters the trading regime of greenhouse gas emissions permits	DL_230_2005_AIR_Portugal.pdf

2005	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 236/2005	Sets limit values to emission of gaseous and particulate pollutants from certain internal combustion engines and transposes Directive 2004/26/EC	DL_236_2005_AIR_Portugal.pdf
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Environmental Policy, Part 2: Water Policy

<i>Year</i>	<i>Type of legislation</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Objective</i>	<i>Data supplied</i>
1976	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros de 23-01-1976 (I Série, publicado em 07-02-1976)	Sets up the Directorate-General of Basic Sanitation Services and basic sanitation regions	RCM_16_03_1976_WATER_Portugal.doc
1976	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 116-A/1976	Transfers to EPAL all the rights and obligations of the Lisbon Water Control Board	DL_116A_1976_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1976	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 117-D/76	Sets up the State Secretariat for Water Resources and Basic Sanitation, the National Council of Water and the Directorates-General of Resources and Basic Sanitation	DL_117D_1976_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1976	Despacho	Despacho de 10-03-1976 (II Série, 24-03-1976)	Sets up the Porto basic sanitation region and nominates the installation committee of the Porto region basic sanitation public services	Hardcopy_Desp_10_03_1976_WATER_Portugal
1976	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros de 16-03-1976 (I Série, 30-03-1976)	Sets up the Lisbon basic sanitation region	RCM_16_03_1976_WATER_Portugal.doc
1976	Despacho	Despacho de 30-04-1976 (II Série, 14-05-1976)	Sets up the Algarve basic sanitation region and nominates the installation committee of the Algarve region basic sanitation public services	Hardcopy_Desp_30_04_1976_WATER_Portugal
1976	Decreto	Decreto n.º 438/76	Defines the National Water Council responsibilities and sets norms relating to its operations	D_438_1976_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1976	Despacho	Despacho de 04-06-1976 (II Série, 22-06-1976)	Sets up the Beira Alta basic sanitation region and nominates the installation committee of the Beira Alta region basic sanitation public services	Hardcopy_Desp_04_06_1976_WATER_Portugal
1976	Despacho	Despacho de 07-06-1976 (II Série, 24-06-1976)	Nominates a work group to prepare setting up the Lisbon region basic sanitation public services	Hardcopy_Desp_07_06_1976_WATER_Portugal
1976	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 569/76	Requires works without municipal permits to be submitted to the appraisal of the sanitation authorities as well as those with municipal permits but which could be of a real or potential danger to public health, especially as a result of their solid, liquid or gaseous waste	DL_569_1976_WATER_Portugal.doc
1976	Decreto	Decreto n.º 694/76, D.R. n.º 222, Série I de 1976-09-21.	Approves, for ratification, the International Convention on Civil Liability for Oil Pollution Damage, concluded 29 November 1969	D_694_1976_WATER_Portugal.doc
1976	Despacho	Despacho de 01-10-1976 (II Série, 11-11-1976)	Sets up a commission to study and revise all legislation on the water systems	Hardcopy_Desp_01_10_1976_WATER_Portugal
1976	Despacho	Despacho de 04-12-1976 (II Série, 23-12-1976)	Extends the working period of the installation committee of the Beira Alta region basic sanitation public services	Hardcopy_Desp_04_12_1976_WATER_Portugal

1977	Despacho	Despacho Conjunto de 30-05-1977 (II Série, 08-07-1977)	Sets up a Basic Sanitation work group – World Health Organization + Portuguese government	Hardcopy_DC_30_05_1977_ WATER_Portugal
1977	Despacho	Despacho de 01-04-1977 (II Série, 27-05-1977)	Extends the work period of the installation committee of the Porto region basic sanitation public services	Hardcopy_Desp_01_04_1977_ WATER_Portugal
1977	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 254/77	Approves the organisational structure of the Basic Sanitation Directorate-General Services	DL_254_1977_ WATER_Portugal.pdf
1977	Despacho	Despacho de 18-07-1977 (II Série, 04-08-1977)	Extends the work period of the installation committee of the Beira Alta region basic sanitation public services	Hardcopy_Desp_18_07_1977_ WATER_Portugal
1977	Lei	Lei n.º 46/77	Forbids the participation of private companies and other entities of the same nature (demarcation sector law) in the economic activities of catchment, treatment and distribution of water for public consumption, collection, treatment and disposal of effluents and solid waste, and telecommunications	L_46_1977_ WATER_Portugal.pdf
1977	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei 376/77	Requires prior permission and certain conditions to be met for well-digging and extracting subterranean water in several municipalities in the Coimbra, Leiria and Setúbal districts	DL_376_1977_ WATER_Portugal.pdf
1977	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 383/77	Approves the Organic Law of the Directorate-General of Hydraulic Resources and their Exploitation	DL_383_1977_ WATER_Portugal.pdf
1977	Despacho	Despacho Conjunto de 31-10-1977 (II Série, 21-12-1977)	Sets up the Baixa Alentejo Basic Sanitation Region	Hardcopy_DC_31_10_1977_ WATER_Portugal
1978	Decreto	Decreto n.º 1/78	Approves, for ratification, the Convention on the Prevention of Marine Pollution from Land-based Sources (Paris, 1974)	D_1_1978_ WATER_Portugal.pdf
1978	Decreto	Decreto n.º 2/78	Approves, for ratification, the Convention on the Prevention of Marine Pollution by Dumping of Wastes and Other Matter (London, 1972)	D_2_1978_ WATER_Portugal.pdf
1978	Lei	Lei n.º 3/78	Re-drafts several articles of Decree-Law No. 254/77, of 15 June, which approves the organisational structure of the Basic Sanitation Directorate-General	L_3_1978_ WATER_Portugal.pdf
1978	Portaria	Portaria n.º 764/78	Approves the revision of norm NP-730 on “Determining the amount of ammoniacal nitrogen in water”	P_764_1978_ WATER_Portugal.pdf
1979	Portaria	Portaria n.º 251/79	Extends to Portugal’s various regions the legal provisions in Decree-Law No. 376/77, of 5 September, which prior permission and certain conditions to be met for well-digging and extracting subterranean water in several municipalities in the Coimbra, Leiria and Setúbal districts	P_251_1979_ WATER_Portugal.pdf

1979	Portaria	Portaria n.º 323/79	Alters Nos. 1 and 2 of Ordinance (<i>Portaria</i>) No 251/79, which extends to Portugal's regions the legal provisions in Decree-Law No. 376/77, relating to the extraction of subterranean water	P_323_1979_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1980	no legislative activity			
1981	Portaria	Portaria n.º 158/81	Approves and executes regulatory norms of Decree Law No. 233/79, which establishes norms relating to the classification of pig farming. Includes provisions with regard to its waste management	P_158_1981_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1982	no legislative activity			
1983	no legislative activity			
1984	Portaria	Portaria n.º 588/84	Classifies mainland Portugal's beaches as 1st, 2nd and 3rd categories according to the table approved by Decree 12 822, of 1 November 1926	P_588_1984_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1984	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 29/84	Sets up a commission to study institutional manners of water management under the State Secretary for Land Use Planning	RCM_29_1984_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1985	Decreto do Governo	Decreto do Governo n.º 13/85	Approves, for ratification, the International Convention on the Establishment of an International Fund for Compensation for Oil Pollution Damage, 1971, and, for adhesion, the 1976 Protocol to the same convention	DG_13_1985_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1985	Portaria	Portaria n.º 43/85	Extends to the municipalities of Alenquer, Amadora, Azambuja, Cascais, Lisboa, Loures, Oeiras, Sintra and Vila Franca de Xira, the dispositions in No. 1 of Article 1 of Decree-Law 376/77, on extracting water from aquiferous formations	P_43_1985_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1985	Declaração de Rectificação	Declaração de Rectificação de 30-09-1985	Oil pollution – Rectifies Government Decree No. 13/85	DRec_30_09_1985_WATER_Portugal.doc
1986	no legislative activity			
1987	Despacho Conjunto	Despacho Conjunto de 16-04-1987 (II Série)	Sets up the Tagus Integrated Water Resources Management Project (PGIRH/T)	Hardcopy_DC_16_04_1987_WATER_Portugal
1987	Lei	Lei n.º 11/87	Foundations of Environmental Law – General Principles defend measures that ensure water quality	L_11_87_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1987	Decreto do Governo	Decreto do Governo n.º 20/87	Approves, for ratification, the Protocol Altering the Convention for the Prevention of Maritime Pollution Caused by Immersion Operations of Sea- and Airships, made in Oslo on February 15, 1972, and the Code of Practice for Incineration of Residues at Sea, established by said Protocol	DG_20_1987_WATER_Portugal.pdf

1987	Decreto do Governo	Decreto do Governo n.º 25/87	Approves for accession the 1978 Protocol, made in London on February 17, 1978, concerning the International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution by Ships, of 1973	DG_25_1987_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1987	Portaria	Portaria n.º 752/87	Approves internal regulations of the Commission of Public Maritime Domain	P_752_1987_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1987	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 230/87	Establishes preventative measures for the area of the Lagoon of Albufeira (in the Municipality of Sesimbra)	DL_230_1987_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1987	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 384/87	Establishes the regime to make programme-contracts of a sectorial or multi-sectorial nature within the scope of technical and financial cooperation between the central administration and one or more municipalities, associations of municipalities or their concessionary companies (including basic sanitation or the installation of depollution systems)	DL_384_1987_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1988	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 2/88	Classifies, in application of Decree-Law No. 502/71, public water supply reservoirs	DR_2_1988_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1988	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 91/88	Sets up the Estoril Basic Sanitation Office	DL_91_1988_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1988	Portaria	Portaria n.º 445/88	Regulates administrative proceedings needed for the authorisation process of the hydroelectric exploitation of water	P_445_1988_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1988	Aviso	Aviso n.º 176 de 1988-08-01.	Makes public that Portugal has deposited the instrument of ratification of the 1978 protocol of the International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution by Ships, of 1973	A_1_08_1988_WATER_Portugal.doc
1988	Decreto	Decreto n.º 25/88	Approves, for ratification, the protocol that introduces amendments to the 1974 Convention on the Prevention of Marine Pollution from Land-based Sources	D_25_1988_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1988	Decreto	Decreto n.º 33/88	Approves amendments to the Convention on the Prevention of Marine Pollution by Dumping of Wastes and Other Matter	D_33_1988_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1988	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 449/88	Alters some dispositions in Law No. 46/77 relating to sector demarcation	DL_449_1988_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1988	Despacho Normativo	Despacho Normativo n.º 66/88	Estabelece um regulamento para apresentação e selecção das candidaturas a contratos-programa nas áreas do saneamento básico, ambiente e recursos naturais Establishes regulations to the presentation of applications to programme-contracts on basic sanitation, environment and natural resources	DN_66_1988_WATER_Portugal.pdf

1989	Portaria	Portaria n.º 151/89	Sets up a zone for the protection of the aquiferous systems that feed the Vale de Maiais catchment area	P_151_1989_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1989	Portaria	Portaria n.º 752/87	Internal regulation of the Public Domain Commission (first referred to in 1892 - Decreto n.º 8)	P_752_1987_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1989	Portaria	Portaria n.º 958/89	Redrafts various numbers of Ordinance (<i>Portaria</i>) No 445/88, which regulates administrative proceedings needed for the authorisation process of hydroelectric exploitation of water	P_958_1989_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1990	Decreto	Decreto n.º 4/90	Approves the amendments made to annexes I and II of the Convention for the Prevention of Maritime Pollution Caused by Immersion Operations of Sea- and Airships, of 1972	D_4_1990_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1990	Portaria	Portaria n.º 134/90	Classifies beaches in mainland Portugal. Repeals Ordinance (<i>Portaria</i>) No. 588/84	P_134_1990_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1990	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 70/90	Defines the regime of assets of state public domain water - In order to promote planning and management of water resources in a rational manner, the hydrographic basin, a combination of hydrographic basins and areas so considered from the standpoint of water use, have been defined as a management unit, thereby setting up the water resources administrations (ARHs).	DL_70_1990_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1990	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 74/90	Based on the «water cycle» concept, it sets minimum quality standards that a water must meet depending on its use. It empowers several bodies to carry out the diploma's principles, especially water resources management and quality promotion, as well as with regard to licensing, inspection and ensuring regulations are complied with. It sets up a Water Quality Consultative Commission to regulate its composition and attributions	DL_74_1990_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1990	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 84/90	Approves spring water exploitation regulations	DL_84_1990_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1990	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 85/90	Approves industrial mineral water regulations	DL_85_1990_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1990	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 86/90	Approves natural mineral water regulations	DL_86_1990_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1990	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 90/90	Organises the general regime for finding and exploiting geological resources, including subterranean water	DL_90_1990_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1990	Declaração	Declaração de 1990-03-31	Declares corrections made to Decree-Law No. 74/90, which approves water quality standards	DRec_31_03_1990_WATER_Portugal.doc

1990	Portaria	Portaria n.º 624/90	Approves standards to apply for waste water discharge from isolated and clusters of dwellings, and all sectors of human activity.	P_624_1990_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1990	Despacho	Despacho n.º 36/DGL/1990 de 16-08-1990 (II Série)	Sets an adaptation period for the pulp and paper industry to start applying waste water discharge standards	Hardcopy_Desp_36_DGL_1990_WATER_Portugal
1990	Despacho Conjunto	Despacho Conjunto de 16-06-1990	Creates an Evaluation Commission on the Guadiana River usage, in the area of Alqueva	DC_16_06_1990_WATER_Portugal.doc
1990	Portaria	Portaria n.º 809/90	Approves standards for waste water discharge from slaughterhouses and meat processing units	P_809_1990_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1990	Portaria	Portaria n.º 810/90	Approves standards relating to waste water discharge from all pig farms	P_810_1990_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1990	Portaria	Portaria n.º 839/90	Extends to the Cartaxo, Santiago do Cacém and Sines municipalities No. 1 of Article No. 1 of Decree-Law 376/77, which regulates water extraction in aquiferous formations	P_839_1990_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1990	Decreto	Decreto n.º 48/90	Approves for accession the 1984 amendments made to the annex to the International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution by Ships (MARPOL 73)	D_48_1990_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1990	Declaração	Declaração de 31-12-1990	Declares that Decree-Law No. 74/90, which approves water quality standards, has been rectified	DRec_31_12_1990_WATER_Portugal.doc
1990	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 43/90	Promotes the execution of public works projects in the Ave River Valley within national operational/sectorial programmes, including aspects related to sanitation	RCM_43_1990_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1991	Portaria	Portaria n.º 372/91	Classifies beaches in mainland Portugal. Repeals Ordinance (<i>Portaria</i>) No. 134/90	P_372_1991_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1991	Decreto	Decreto n.º 37/91	Approves the Cooperation Agreement for the Protection of the Coasts and Waters of the North- East Atlantic against Pollution	D_37_1991_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1991	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 37/91	Alters Regulatory Decree No. 2/88, which classifies public water supply reservoirs, for effects of applying Decree-Law No. 502/71,	DR_37_1991_WATER_Portugal.doc
1991	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 283/91	Transposes into national legislation Directive 80/777/EC, relating to the exploitation and marketing of natural mineral waters	DL_283_1991_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1991	Portaria	Portaria n.º 834/91	Approves the composition, powers and internal regulations of the Water Quality Consultative Commission	P_834_1991_WATER_Portugal.pdf

1991	Decreto	Decreto n.º 50/91	Approves, for accession, the amendments altering the International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution by Ships, modified by the 1978 protocol (MARPOL 73-78)	D_50_1991_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1991	Portaria	Portaria n.º 946/91 de 17-09-1991	Appends a paragraph to No. 4 of the Water Quality Consultative Commission, whereby a representative of the General-Direction of Natural Resources must also be included in its composition	P_946_1991_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1991	<i>Decreto-Lei</i>	<i>Decreto-Lei n.º 339/91</i>	Alters Law No. 46/77 (Sector Demarcation Law), with the drafting provided in Decree-Law No. 449/88	DL_339_1991_Water_Portugal.pdf
1992	Decreto	Decreto n.º 13/92	Approves, for accession, the Protocol Amending the Convention for the Prevention of Maritime Pollution Caused by Immersion Operations of Sea- and Airships	D_13_1992_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1992	Portaria	Portaria n.º 333/92	Establishes norms relating to the preparation of land use plans for classified reservoirs	P_333_1992_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1992	Portaria	Portaria n.º 363/92	Classifies beaches in mainland Portugal. Repeals Ordinance (<i>Portaria</i>) No. 372/91	P_363_1992_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1992	Portaria	Portaria n.º 505/92	Establishes waste water discharge standards for the pulp and paper industry	P_505_1992_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1992	Portaria	Portaria n.º 512/92	Establishes waste water discharge standards for the tanning industry	P_512_1992_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1992	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 18/92	Approves natural mineral water regulations	DR_18_1992_WATER_Portugal.doc
1992	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 22/92	Approves the Regional Land Use Plan for the land surrounding the Aguieira, Coiço and Fronhas reservoirs (PROZAG).	DR_22_1992_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1992	Despacho	Despacho n.º 12/DGQA/1992 de 11-09-1992 (II Série)	Establishes waste water discharge standards for surface treatment systems	Hardcopy_Desp_12_DGQA_1992_WATER_Portugal
1992	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 33/92	Alters Regulatory Decree No.2/88, which classifies water supply reservoirs, for the effects of applying Decree-Law No. 502/71	DR_33_1992_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1993	Decreto	Decreto n.º 3/93	Approves, for accession, the amendments to the Annex to the 1978 Protocol concerning the International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution by Ships	D_3_1993_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1993	Portaria	Portaria n.º 324/93	Defines conditions that natural mineral waters must meet to be considered bacteriologically suitable for drinking	P_324_1993_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1993	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 25/93	Approves the Clean Sea plan. Defines a set of norms to act upon in whatever kind of emergency that arises due to oil or other dangerous pollutant spillage, and establishes the responsibilities borne	RCM_25_1993_WATER_Portugal.pdf

			by each party involved in mainland Portugal and Autonomous Regions in order to prevent and combat the negative effects of these accidents. Sets up an inter-ministerial commission consisting of the Ministers for National Defence, Internal Administration, Environment and Natural Resources, and Sea, with global supervisory functions over the institutionalised operational system and defines the necessary guidelines to carry them out.	
1993	Despacho Conjunto	Despacho Conjunto de 26-04-1993 (II Série)	Pollution in Ria de Aveiro – Work groups formed to examine Ria de Aveiro pollution	DC_26_04_1993_WATER_Portugal.doc
1993	Despacho Conjunto	Despacho Conjunto de 08-06-1993 (II Série)	Approves the Castelo de Bode reservoir land use plan, and establishes its respective goals	DC_08_06_1993_WATER_Portugal.doc
1993	Despacho Conjunto	Despacho Conjunto de 08-06-1993 (II Série)	Approves the Azibo reservoir Land Use Plan	DC_08_06_1993B_WATER_Portugal.doc
1993	Declaração de Rectificação	Declaração de Rectificação n.º 73/93	Rectifies Ordinance (<i>Portaria</i>) No. 324/93, which defines conditions that natural mineral waters must meet in order to be considered bacteriologically suitable for drinking	DRec_73_1993_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1993	Decreto	Decreto n.º 18/93	Approves, for accession, the amendments to Annex II of the International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution by Ships, modified by the 178 Protocol	D_18_1993_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1993	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 191/93	Creates and establishes the National Institute for Water (INAG) organisational structure	DL_18_1993_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1993	Declaração de Rectificação	Declaração de Rectificação n.º 101/93	Rectifies Council of Ministers Resolution 25/93, which approves the Clean Seas Plan	DRec_101_1993_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1993	Despacho	Despacho n.º 54/SERN/1993 de 13-07-1993 (II Série)	Establishes the procedures for the National Water Institute (INAG) and the Regional Directorates for the Environment and Natural Resources (DRARNs) to adopt in waste water discharge licensing	Hardcopy_Desp_54_SERN_1993_WATER_Portugal
1993	Aviso	Aviso n.º 180/93.	Makes public that Portugal has deposited the letters of accession to the December 5, 1989 Protocol amending the Convention for the Prevention of Maritime Pollution Caused by Immersion Operations of Sea- and Airships (1972 Oslo Convention)	A_180_1993_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1993	Despacho Conjunto	Despacho Conjunto de 13-07-1993	Approves the Caia reservoir Land Use Plan	DC_13_07_1993_WATER_Portugal.pdf

1993	Despacho Conjunto	Despacho Conjunto de 17-08-1993	Approves the Gameiro reservoir Land Use Plan	DC_17_08_1993_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1993	Declaração de Rectificação	Declaração de Rectificação n.º 155/93	Declares the rectification of Decreto n.º 18/93, of the Foreign Affairs Ministry, which approves, for accession, the amendment to Annex II of the Convention for the Prevention of Pollution by Ships, modified by the 1978 Protocol	DRec_155_1993_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1993	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 28/93	Classifies the Monte Fidalgo (Cedilho) reservoir	DR_28_1993_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1993	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1030/93	Establishes standards relating to waste water discharge into the natural environment (water or soil) of industrial units of the surface treatment sector	P_1030_1993_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1993	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1033/93	Establishes standards relating to waste water discharge applicable to industrial units in which chlor-alkali electrolysis is processed	P_1033_1993_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1993	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1049/93	Establishes standards relating to waste water discharge applicable to all industrial activities that involve handling asbestos	P_1049_1993_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1993	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 309/93	Regulates the elaboration and approval of land use planning of coastal zone (altered by Decree-Law No. 218/94, of 20 August, see Decree-Law No. 290/95, of 10 November).	DL_309_1993_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1993	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 372/93	Alters Law No. 46/77 (sector demarcation law) with regard to private entities and other similar entities having access to the economic activities of catchment, treatment and distribution of water for public consumption, the collection, treatment and rejection of effluents and solid waste, and telecommunications	DL_372_1993_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1993	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 379/93	Authorises private capital to access economic activities of the catchment, treatment and disposal of effluents and collecting and treating solid waste	DL_379_1993_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1993	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1109/93	Updates rates to apply for services involving the discharge, reception and treatment of industrial effluents and treatment of solid waste and mud contaminated by oily residues received in the appropriate place	P_1109_1993_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1994	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 45/94	Sets up the National Water Council (CNA) as a consultative body for national water resource planning. Regulates the process of water resource planning and the elaboration and approval of water resource plans, especially the National Water Plan and the Hydrographic Basin Plans	DL_45_1994_WATER_Portugal.pdf

1994	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 46/94	Establishes the regime for the licensing of demesial water use, under the jurisdiction of the National Water Institute (including provisions relating to limiting waste water in water and soil)	DL_46_1994_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1994	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 47/94	Establishes the economic and financial regime of demesial water use, under the jurisdiction of the National Institute of Water	DL_47_1994_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1994	Portaria	Portaria n.º 327/94	Classifies beaches in mainland Portugal and repeals Ordinance (<i>Portaria</i>) No. 363/92	P_327_1994_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1994	Decreto	Decreto n.º 22/94	Approves, for ratification, the Convention on the Protection and Use of Transboundary Watercourses and International Lakes	D_22_1994_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1994	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 33-A/94	Establishes measures relating to the Ave Valley intervention programme, including, within the environmental sphere, certain aspects related to the Ave Valley Integrated Depollution System (SIDVA)	RCM_33-A_1994_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1994	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 97/94	Entrusts the Alentejo Region Coordination Commission with promoting the elaboration of the Alqueva Reservoir Regional Land Use Plan (PROZEA).	RCM_97_1994_Water_Portugal.pdf
1994	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 218/94	Alters Decree-Law No. 309/93, of 2 September (regulating the elaboration and approval of coastal zones land use planning)	DL_218_1994_Water_Portugal.pdf
1994	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 207/94	Approves the conception, installation and exploration of public and land systems of water distribution and waste water drainage	DL_207_1994_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1994	Despacho Conjunto	Despacho Conjunto de 25-08-1994 (II Série)	Inclusion of the National Institute of Water in the work group to examine the aquaculture sector situation and proposal of concrete solutions, created by joint order of 22 March 1994	Hardcopy_DC_25_08_1994_WATER_Portugal
1994	Despacho	Despacho n.º 43/MARN/94 de 19-09-1994 (II Série)	Identifies the organisations with competence to determine fines on marine pollution infractions	D_43_MARN_94_WATER_Portugal.doc
1994	Portaria	Portaria n.º 895/94	Establishes limit values on discharge into water and soil, and quality aims for certain so-called “hazardous” substances (1,2-dichloroethane, trichloroethylene, perchloroethylene, trichlorobenzene) with a view to eliminating or reducing the pollution they may cause this environment	P_895_1994_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1994	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 319/94	Establishes the legal system for the construction, exploitation and management of multi-municipal systems for the catchment and treatment of water for public consumption when attributed by concession, and approves the	DL_319_1994_WATER_Portugal.pdf

			respective bases	
1994	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1147/94	Establishes licensing conditions for the discharge, storage, disposal or injection into the soil of waste water and titanium dioxide industrial waste	P_1147_1994_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1995	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 23/95	Approves the general regulations of the public and land systems of water distribution and waste water drainage	DR_23_1995_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1995	Aviso	Aviso n.º 46/95	Makes known that Portugal deposited its instrument of confirmation and ratification of the Convention on the Protection and Use of Transboundary Watercourses and International Lakes (Helsinki, 17 March 1992)	A_46_1995_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1995	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 32/95	Sets up the Alqueva Development and Infrastructures Company S.A.	DL_32_1995_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1995	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 33/95	Adopts preventative measures relating to areas included in the Alqueva Multipurpose Development Project	DL_33_1995_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1995	Decreto-lei	Decreto-Lei 116/95	Sets up the Águas do Douro e Paiva concessionary company	DL_116_1995_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1995	Decreto-lei	Decreto-Lei 130/95	Sets up the Águas do Sotavento Algarvio concessionary company	DL_130_1995_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1995	Decreto-lei	Decreto-Lei 136/95	Sets up the Águas do Barlavento Algarvio concessionary company	DL_136_1995_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1995	Decreto-lei	Decreto-Lei 142/95	Sets up the Costa do Estoril Multi-municipal Sanitation System and SANEST – Costa do Estoril Sanitation	DL_142_1995_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1995	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 147/95	Sets up a national observatory of mulimunicipal and municipal systems for the catchment, treatment and distribution of water for public consumption, of the collection, treatment and rejection of effluents and the collection and treatment of solid waste and regulates the legal regime of municipal systems concession	DL_147_1995_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1995	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 151/95	Harmonises the legal regime for Special Land Use Planning. Defines Special Plans for Land Use Planning as those relating to protected areas, reservoir plans and coast plans	DL_151_1995_Water_Portugal.pdf
1995	Portaria	Portaria n.º 927/95	Classifies beaches mainland Portugal. Repeals Ordinance (<i>Portaria</i>) No. 327/94	P_927_1995_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1995	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 23/95	Approves general regulations for public and property water distribution and waste water drainage	DR_23_1995_WATER_Portugal.pdf

1995	Despacho	Despacho n.º 38/MARN/95, de 12 de Setembro	Sets up a concessions commission for all multimunicipal systems of the catchment, treatment and distribution of water for public consumption, for the collection, treatment and rejection of effluents	Hardcopy_Desp_38_MARN_1995_WATER_Portugal
1995	Despacho conjunto	Despacho conjunto dos Ministérios do Mar e do Ambiente e dos Recursos Naturais, de 27-04-1995 (2.ª Série)	Defines technical regulations to which the dredging and dumping of dredged material must comply, as covered by the Oslo Convention	DC_27_04_1995_WATER_Portugal.doc
1995	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1274/95	Approves regulations on the licensing, classification and registration of pig storehousing (with provisions relating to waste water)	P_1274_1995_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1995	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 290/95	Determines the immediate entry into force of provisions on regulation instruments connected with bathing and beach notices, provided for in Decree-Law No. 309/93, that regulates the elaboration and approval of land use planning along the coast	DL_290_1995_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1995	Declaração de Rectificação	Declaração de Rectificação n.º 153/95	Rectifies Regulatory Decree No. 23/95, which approves general regulations of public and property water distribution and waste water drainage systems	DRec_153_1995_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1995	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 38/95	Approves Environment Policy Plan (PNPA), which includes strategic guidelines for water quality	RCM_38_95_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1995	Despacho conjunto	Despacho conjunto n.º de 03/11/1995 (II Série)	Following the Clean Sea plan, determines some situations in which Portugal may ask for foreign cooperation	Hardcopy_DC_03_11_1995_WATER_Portugal
1996	Lei	Lei n.º 5/96	Alters, for ratification, Decree Law 151/95, which harmonises the legal regime for Special Land Use Planning. Defines Special Plans for Land Use Planning as those relating to protected areas, reservoir plans and coast plans	L_5_1996_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1996	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 162/96	Establishes the legal regime for the construction, exploitation and management of multimunicipal systems for the collection, treatment and rejection of effluents	DL_162_1996_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1996	Declaração de Rectificação	Declaração de Rectificação n.º 16-R/96	Declares the ratification of Decree-Law No 162/96, on multimunicipal systems for the collection, treatment and rejection of effluents	DRec_16R_1996_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1997	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 152/97	Transposes into national law Directive 91/271/EC, relating to urban waste water treatment	DL_152_1997_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1997	Decreto	Decreto n.º 59/97	Approves, for ratification, the Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East	D_59_1997_WATER_Portugal.pdf

			Atlantic, adopted in Paris within the ambit of the ministerial meeting of the Commissions in Oslo and Paris, on 22 September 1992	
1997	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 6/97	Sets up the Ave Valley Integrated Development Programme within a regional, multi-sectorial scope for 1997-1999, together with the municipalities of Fafe, Guimarães, Póvoa de Lanhoso, Santo Tirso, Vieira do Minho and Vila Nova de Famalicão, including within the environment area aspects related to the Ave Valley Integrated Depollution System (SIDVA)	RCM_6_1997_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1997	Portaria	Portaria n.º 423/97	Establishes standards for waste water discharge specifically applicable to industrial textile sector units, excluding the wool sub-sector	P_423_1997_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1997	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 166/97	Defines the structure, jurisdiction and workings of the National Water Council (CNA), the consultative body of national planning for water, in which are represented the Public Administration and national professional, scientific and financial organisations that are most concerned in the various uses of water	DL_166_1997_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1997	Lei	Lei n.º 88-A/97	Regulates access of private economic initiative to certain economic activities, namely: catchment, treatment and distribution of water for public consumption, the collection, treatment and rejection of urban waste water, by means of fixed networks	L_88A_1997_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1997	Despacho	Despacho n.º 5921/97 de 14-08-1997 (2.ª Série)	Olive oil production sector – establishes the adaptation period of the water waste discharge regime according to paragraph b) of No. 3 of Article 40 of Decree-Law No.74/90	Hardcopy_Desp_5921_1997_WATER_Portugal
1997	Despacho	Despacho n.º 5922/97 de 14-08-1997 (2.ª Série)	Dairy products sector – establishes the adaptation period of the water waste discharge regime according to paragraph b) of No. 3 of Article No. 40 of Decree Law No. 74/90	Hardcopy_Desp_5922_1997_WATER_Portugal
1997	Despacho	Despacho n.º 5923/97 de 14-08-1997 (2.ª Série) da Direcção Geral do Ambiente	Stone extraction sector and stone-sawing, cutting and finishing sector - establishes the adaptation period of the water waste discharge regime according to paragraph b) of No. 3 of Article No. 40 of Decree Law No. 74/90	Hardcopy_Desp_5923_1997_WATER_Portugal

1997	Despacho	Despacho n.º 5924/97 de 14-08-1997 (2.ª Série)	Animal fats and vegetable oils sectors (excluding olive oil production), along with the soap and detergent manufacturing industry, cleaning and polishing products, perfumes and hygiene materials – establishes the adaptation period of the waste water discharge regime according to paragraph b) of No. 3 of Article No. 40 of Decree Law No. 74/90	Hardcopy_Desp_5924_1997_WATER_Portugal
1997	Despacho	Despacho n.º 5925/97 de 14-08-1997 (2.ª Série)	Chemical product manufacturing sector - establishes the adaptation period of the waste water discharge regime according to paragraph b) of No. 3 of Article No. 40 of Decree Law No. 74/90	Hardcopy_Desp_5925_1997_WATER_Portugal
1997	Despacho	Despacho n.º 5926/97 de 14-08-1997 (2.ª Série)	Paper, cardboard and other paper product manufacturing – must proceed with the waste water discharge regime until 31 July 1998	Hardcopy_Desp_5926_1997_WATER_Portugal
1997	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 235/97	Transposes to national law Directive 91/676/EC concerning the protection of water against pollution caused by nitrates from agricultural sources	DL_235_1997_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1997	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1037/97	Approves list and letter that identifies water and areas mentioned in No. 1 of Article No. 4 of Decree-Law No 235/97	P_1037_1997_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1997	Decreto do Presidente da República	Decreto do Presidente da República n.º 67-A/97	Ratifies the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea, of 10 December 1982, and the agreement relating to the application of Part XI of the Convention, adopted by the UN General Assembly 28 July 1994	DPR_67A_1997_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1997	Resolução da Assembleia da República	Resolução da Assembleia da República n.º 60-B/97	Approves, for ratification, the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea and the Agreement relating to the implementation of Part IX of the Convention	RAR_60B_1997_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1998	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 21/98	Sets up the Reservoirs Management Commission	DL_21_1998_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1998	Despacho	Despacho n.º 2919/98, de 17/02 (2.ª Série)	Establishes the composition of the National Commission for the National Water Plan and the composition of the Planning Units of the Hydro Basin Plans	Hardcopy_Desp_2919_1998_WATER_Portugal
1998	Despacho	Despacho n.º 3215/98, de 21/02 (2.ª Série)	Establishes the deadline for environmental adaptation to the waste water discharge standards in the wood industry and furniture-making sectors	Hardcopy_Desp_3215_1998_WATER_Portugal
1998	Despacho	Despacho n.º 3272/98, de 23/02 (2.ª Série)	Establishes the deadline for environmental adaptation to the waste water discharge standards in the printing sector and related activities	Hardcopy_Desp_3272_1998_WATER_Portugal
1998	Despacho	Despacho n.º 3273/98, de 23/02 (2.ª Série)	Establishes the deadline for environmental adaptation to the waste water discharge standards in the shoe-making industry, its components, leather articles and similar	Hardcopy_Desp_3273_1998_WATER_Portugal

1998	Despacho	Despacho n.º 5142/98, de 27/03 (2.ª Série)	Establishes the deadline for environmental adaptation to the waste water discharge standards in the rubber manufacturing industry	Hardcopy_Desp_5142_1998_WATER_Portugal
1998	Despacho	Despacho n.º 5143/98, de 27/03 (2.ª Série)	Establishes the deadline for environmental adaptation to the waste water discharge standards in the tomato industry sector	Hardcopy_Desp_5143_1998_WATER_Portugal
1998	Despacho	Despacho n.º 5144/98, de 27/03 (2.ª Série)	Establishes the deadline for environmental adaptation to the waste water discharge standards in the industry of pesticides and other agro-chemical products	Hardcopy_Desp_5144_1998_WATER_Portugal
1998	Despacho	Despacho n.º 5145/98, de 27/03 (2.ª Série)	Establishes the deadline for environmental adaptation to the waste water discharge standards in the paint, varnish, masticque, glue and other similar industries	Hardcopy_Desp_5145_1998_WATER_Portugal
1998	Despacho	Despacho n.º 5146/98, de 27 de Março (2.ª Série)	Establishes the deadline for environmental adaptation to the waste water discharge standards in the ceramic industry	Hardcopy_Desp_5146_1998_WATER_Portugal
1998	Despacho	Despacho n.º 5147/98, de 27/03 (2.ª Série)	Establishes the deadline for environmental adaptation to the waste water discharge standards in the cork industry	Hardcopy_Desp_5147_1998_WATER_Portugal
1998	Despacho	Despacho n.º 5148/98, de 27/03 (2.ª Série)	Establishes the deadline for environmental adaptation to the waste water discharge standards in the industries of building, repairing and dismantling of metal and non-metal ships	Hardcopy_Desp_5148_1998_WATER_Portugal
1998	Despacho	Despacho n.º 5149/98, de 27/03 (2.ª Série)	Establishes the deadline for environmental adaptation to the waste water discharge standards in the manufacturing industries of machines and devices, radio and tv sets, and domestic appliances	Hardcopy_Desp_5149_1998_WATER_Portugal
1998	Despacho	Aviso n.º 5699/98, de 7/04 (2.ª Série)	Makes public that economic agents, individual or collective, public or private, whose activity is part of industrial sectors not covered by adaptation ordnances already published, have three months to carry out similar adaptation, so as to accomplish the waste water discharge standards	Hardcopy_A_5699_1998_WATER_Portugal
1998	Lei	Lei n.º 48/98	Establishes the framework policy on Land Use and Urban Planning (including principles and objectives on the sustainable use of natural resources)	L_48_1998_Water_Portugal.pdf
1998	Aviso	Aviso n.º 81/98	Makes public that Portugal has deposited the instrument of ratification of the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea, of December 10, 1982, and the Agreement relating to the implementation of Part IX of the Convention, of July 28, 1994	A_81_1998_WATER_Portugal.pdf

1998	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 37/98	Ratifies the Póvoa and Meadas Reservoir Land Use Plan	RCM_37_1998_Water_Portugal.pdf
1998	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 50/98	Approves the Vigia reservoir Land Use Plan	RCM_50_1998_Water_Portugal.pdf
1998	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 156/98 de 06-06-1998	Establishes regulations relative to recognition as natural mineral water and characteristics and conditions to observe in treatment, labelling and marketing of natural mineral water and spring water, repealing Decree-Law No. 283/91	DL_156_1998_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1998	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 83/98	Establishes guidelines for strategic definition of the national policy for the oceans	RCM_83_1998_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1998	Decreto	Decreto n.º 19/98	Approves, for accession, the amendments of Annex I to the 1978 Protocol of the International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution by Ships, 1973 (MARPOL 73/78), adopted by Resolution MEPC 52 (32)	D_19_1998_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1998	Decreto	Decreto n.º 20/98	Approves, for accession, the 1992 amendments, adopted by Resolution MEPC 51 (32) of the International Maritime Organization, to Annex I to the 1978 Protocol of the International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution by Ships	D_20_1998_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1998	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 192/98	Identifies the ministries with competence to apply and execute the rules prescribed in MARPOL Convention 73/78	DL_192_1998_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1998	Decreto	Decreto n.º 22/98	Approves, for accession, the March 17, 1989 amendments, adopted by Resolution MEPC 34 (27) to Annex II of the 1978 Protocol relating to the International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution by Ships, 1973	D_22_1998_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1998	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 232/98	Alters Decree-Law Nos. 32/95 and 33/95, of 11 February, that respectively set up the Alqueva Development and Infrastructures Company, S.A. and adopts preventative measures related with areas within the Alqueva Multipurpose Development Project intervention zone	DL_232_1998_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1998	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 234/98	Alters Articles Nos. 45, 46, 47 and 48 of Decree-Law No. 46/94, on cleaning and de-blocking water channels	DL_234_1998_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1998	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 236/98	Establishes quality standards, criteria and goals with a view to protecting the aquatic environment and improving water quality according to its main uses. Repeals Decree-Law No. 74/90	DL_236_1998_WATER_Portugal.pdf

1998	Portaria	Portaria n.º 546/98	Approves an action programme for the first vulnerable zone, which is the free ground water reservoir between Eposende and Vila do Conde	P_546_1998_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1998	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 348/98	Alters Decree-Law No. 152/97, which transposes into national law Directive 91/271/EC on urban waste water treatment	DL_348_1998_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1998	Aviso	Aviso n.º 165/98	Makes know that according to the communication from the Secretary-General of the United Nations of 31 July 1998, the French Government deposited on 20 June 1998 its instrument of approval of the Convention on the Protection and Use of Transboundary Watercourses and International Lakes, done in Helsinki, 17 March 1992	A_165_1998_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1998	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 362/98	Approves the statute of the Water and Waste Regulatory Institute and extinguishes the National Environment Observatory. Partially repeals Decree-Law No. 147/95	DL_362_1998_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1998	Despacho conjunto	Despacho conjunto n.º 811/98 de 23 de Novembro (II Série)	Sets guidelines relating to the financing and indebtedness of the environmental industries of capture, treatment and distribution of water for human consumption, of capture, treatment and rejection of effluents and capture, treatment and valorisation of solid urban residues	Hardcopy_DC_811_1998_WATER_Portugal
1998	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 151/98	Approves the Alvito reservoir Land Use Plan	RCM_151_1998_Water_Portugal.pdf
1998	Declaração de Rectificação	Declaração de Rectificação n.º 22-C/98	Declares having rectified Decree-Law No. 236/98, which establishes quality standards, criteria and goals with a view to protecting the aquatic environment and improving water quality in its main uses	DRec_22C_1998_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1999	Despacho conjunto	Despacho conjunto 116/99	Determines the composition of the commission to follow the execution of urban water treatment, according to Decree-Law No. 152/97	DC_116_1999_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1999	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 52/99	Transposes into national law Directive 84/156/EC on limit values and quality objectives for mercury discharges by sectors other than the chlor-alkali electrolysis industry	DL_52_1999_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1999	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 53/99	Transposes into national law Directive 83/513/EC on limit values and quality objectives for cadmium discharges	DL_53_1999_WATER_Portugal.pdf

1999	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 54/99	Transposes into national law Directive 84/491/EC on limit values and quality objectives for discharges of hexachlorocyclohexane	DL_54_1999_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1999	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 56/99	Transposes into national law Directive 86/280/EC on limit values and quality objectives for discharges of certain dangerous substances, and Directive 88/347/EC, which alters Annex II of Directive 86/280/EC	DL_56_1999_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1999	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 68/99	Alters Decree-Law No. 235/97, on the protection of water against agricultural nitrate pollution	DL_68_1999_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1999	Portaria	Portaria n.º 429/99	Establishes limit values on industrial waste water discharge on water or soil	P_429_1999_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1999	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 261/99	Alters Decree-Law No. 152/97, with the legislative drafting it was given by Decree-Law No. 348/98, which transposes into national law Directives 91/271/EC and 98/15/EC respectively on urban waste water treatment	DL_261_1999_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1999	Despacho conjunto	Despacho conjunto, N.º 660/99, de 09-08-1999 (II Série)	Approves working regulations of the Reservoir Management Commission	DC_660_1999_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1999	Decreto do Presidente da República	Decreto do Presidente da República n.º 182/99	Ratifies the Convention on Cooperation for the Protection and Sustainable Use of Water in the Portuguese-Spanish River Basins and its Additional Protocol, signed in Albufeira, 30 November 1998	DPR_182_1999_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1999	Resolução da Assembleia da República	Resolução da Assembleia da República n.º 66/99	Approves, for ratification, the Convention on Cooperation for the Protection and Sustainable Use of Water in the Portuguese-Spanish River Basins and its Additional Protocol, signed in Albufeira, 30 November 1998	RAR_66_1999_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1999	Portaria	Portaria n.º 744-A/99	Approves specific action programmes to prevent or eliminate pollution from multiple sources of mercury	P_744A_1999_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1999	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 380/99	Establishes the legislation action programme foreseen in Law No. 48/98, which defines the coordination organisation for the national, regional and municipal land management system, the general organisation of land use and the organisation for elaborating, approving, executing and monitoring instruments of land management	DL_380_1999_Water_Portugal.pdf
1999	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 382/99	Establishes parameters for the protection of catchment areas of subterranean water for public water supply	DL_382_1999_WATER_Portugal.pdf

1999	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 390/99	Alters Decree-Law No. 56/99, which transposes into national law Directive 86/280/EC on limit values and quality objectives for discharges of certain dangerous substances, and Directive 88/347/EC, which alters Annex II of Directive 86/280/EC	DL_390_1999_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1999	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 431/99	Transposes into national law Directive 82/176/EC on limit values and quality objectives for mercury discharges by the chlor-alkali electrolysis industry. Repeals Ordinance (<i>Portaria</i>) No. 1033/93	DL_431_1999_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1999	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 25/99	Classifies Sabugal reservoir as a protected reservoir	DR_25_1999_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1999	Portaria	Portaria n.º 958/99	Sets the parameters for the protection of natural mineral water, which corresponds with registration No. HM-31 and the designation «Caldas do Gerês»	P_958_1999_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1999	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	<i>Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 117/99</i>	Approves the Maranhão Reservoir Land Use Plan	RCM_117_1999_Water_Portugal.pdf
1999	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 139/99	Makes the area under the Castelo do Bode reservoir land use planning subject to preventive measures	RCM_139_1999_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1999	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 506/99	Sets quality objectives in surface waters for certain hazardous substances included in the families or groups of substances on list II of Annex II of Decree-Law No. 236/98	DL_506_1999_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1999	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1060/99	Sets the parameters for the protection of natural mineral water, which corresponds to registration No. HM-22 and the designation «Caldas de Penacova»	P_1060_1999_WATER_Portugal.pdf
1999	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei 543/99	Sets up the Lis multimunicipal sanitation system for the collection, treatment and rejection of effluents of the Batalha, Leiria, Marinha Grande, Ourém and Porto de Mós municipalities	DL_543_1999_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2000	Portaria	Portaria n.º 39/2000	Approves the specific programme to prevent or eliminate pollution from multiple sources of hexachlorobutadiene	P_39_2000_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2000	Despacho conjunto	Despacho conjunto n.º 118/2000 (Série II)	Environmental adaptation of olive oil presses	DC_118_2000_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2000	Portaria	Portaria n.º 91/2000	Approves specific action programmes foreseen in No. 1 of Article No. 8 of Decree-Law No. 56/99 aimed at preventing or eliminating chlorophorm pollution	P_91_2000_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2000	Portaria	Portaria n.º 462/2000 (II Série)	Establishes the National Organic Plan for the protection and improvement of surface drinking water for the production of water for human consumption	P_462_2000_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2000	Despacho conjunto	Despacho conjunto n.º 626/2000	Establishes the set of standards for the proper use of olive oil mill waste water	DC_626_2000_WATER_Portugal.pdf

2000	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 120/2000	Establishes the structure of the Ministry of the Environment and Land Use Planning (MCOTA)	DL_120_2000_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2000		Decreto-Lei n.º 128/2000	Sets up the North Alentejo multimunicipal water supply and sanitation system for the catchment, treatment and distribution of water for public consumption and the collection, treatment and rejection of effluents from the Alter do Chão, Arronches, Avis, Campo Maior, Castelo de Vide, Crato, Elvas, Fronteira, Gavião, Marvão, Monforte, Nisa, Ponte de Sor, Portalegre and Sousel municipalities	DL_128_2000_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2000	Despacho	Despacho n.º 13799/2000	Sets up a work group aimed at examining and suggesting measures aimed at reforming the legal and institutional framework of the water sector	Desp_13799_2000_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2000	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 139/2000	Sets up the Baixo Cávado and Ave multimunicipal system for the collection, treatment and rejection of effluents from the Barcelos, Esposende, Póvoa de Varzim, Vila do Conde and Vila Nova de Famalicão municipalities	DL_139_2000_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2000	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 158/2000	Sets up the Minho-Lima water supply and sanitation multimunicipal system for the catchment, treatment and supply of water for public consumption and the collection, treatment and rejection of effluents from the Arcos de Valdevez, Caminha, Melgaço, Monção, Paredes de Coura, Ponte de Lima, Valença, Viana do Castelo and Vila Nova de Cerveira municipalities and constitutes the system's concessionary	DL_158_2000_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2000	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 167/2000	Sets up the Algarve multimunicipal sanitation system for the collection, treatment and rejection of effluents from the Albufeira, Alcoutim, Aljezur, Castro Marim, Faro, Lagoa, Lagos, Loulé, Monchique, Olhão, Portimão, São Brás de Alportel, Silves, Tavira, Vila do Bispo and Vila Real de Santo António municipalities	DL_167_2000_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2000	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 168/2000	Sets up the concessionary company Águas do Algarve, S. A. by the merger of Águas do Sotavento Algarvio, S. A. with Águas do Barlavento Algarvio, S. A., which were constituted respectively by Decree-Laws Nos. 130/95 and 136/95, and approves their respective statutes	DL_168_2000_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2000	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 194/2000	Transposes into national law Directive 96/61/EC on integrated pollution prevention and control	DL_194_2000_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2000	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 235/2000	Establishes infractions within the scope of marine environment pollution in maritime areas under national	DL_235_2000_WATER_Portugal.pdf

			jurisdiction	
2000	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 260/2000	Sets up the Greater Porto multimunicipal sanitation system for the collection, treatment and rejection of effluents from the Amarante, Arouca, Baião, Cabeceiras de Basto, Castelo de Paiva, Castro Daire, Celorico de Basto, Cinfães, Felgueiras, Gondomar, Lousada, Marco de Canaveses, Matosinhos, Mondim de Basto, Paços de Ferreira, Paredes, Penafiel, Porto and Vila Nova de Paiva municipalities	DL_260_2000_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2000	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 152/2000	Alters the drafting of No. 2 in the Council of Ministers Resolution No. 139/99, establishing a two-year period of duration for preventive measures within the area included in the Castelo do Bode Reservoir Land Use Plan	RCM_152_2000_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2000	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 305-A/2000	Sets up the West multimunicipal water supply and sanitation system for the catchment, treatment and distribution of water for public consumption and the collection, treatment and rejection of effluents from the Alcobça, Alenquer, Arruda dos Vinhos, Azambuja, Bombarral, Cadaval, Caldas da Rainha, Lourinhã, Nazaré, Óbidos, Peniche, Rio Maior, Sobral de Monte Agraço and Torres Vedras municipalities	DL_305-A_2000_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2001	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 105/2001	Sets up the concessionary company Águas do Norte Alentejano, S. A., for the north Alentejo water supply and sanitation exploration and management of the catchment, treatment and distribution of water for public consumption and the collection, treatment and rejection of effluents from the Alter do Chão, Arronches, Avis, Campo Maior, Castelo de Vide, Crato, Elvas, Fronteira, Gavião, Marvão, Monforte, Nisa, Ponte de Sor, Portalegre and Sousel municipalities, which was set up by Decree-Law No. 128/2000	DL_105_2001_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2001	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 171/2001	Sets up the concessionary company Águas de Santo André, S. A., for the exploration and management of the Santo André water supply, sanitation and solid waste treatment	DL_171_2001_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2001	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 172/2001	Partially alters Annex II of Decree-Law No. 152/97, which transposes to national law Directive 91/271/EC on urban waste water treatment	DL_172_2001_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2001	Portaria	Portaria n.º 573/2001	Approves the National Organic Plan for improving non-conforming bathing areas, which implements Directives 76/160/CEE	P_573_2001_WATER_Portugal.pdf

2001	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 197-A/2001	Sets up the Raia, Zêzere and Nabão Cria multimunicipal water supply and sanitation system for the catchment, treatment and distribution of water for public consumption and the collection, treatment and rejection of effluents from the Alvaiázere, Castanheira de Pêra, Castelo Branco, Ferreira do Zêzere, Figueiró dos Vinhos, Idanha-a-Nova, Oleiros, Pampilhosa da Serra, Pedrógão Grande, Proença-a-Nova, Sertã, Tomar and Vila Velha de Ródão municipalities	DL_197-A_2001_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2001	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 243/2001	Approves standards on the quality of water intended for human consumption, transposing into national law Directive 98/83/EC	DL_243_2001_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2001	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 264/2001	Sets up the Baixo Cávado and Ave multimunicipal water supply and sanitation system for the catchment, treatment and distribution of water for public consumption and the collection, treatment and rejection of effluents from the Barcelos, Esposende, Maia, Póvoa de Varzim, Santo Tirso, Trofa, Vila do Conde e Vila Nova de Famalicão municipalities	DL_264_2001_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2001	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 270-A/2001	Sets up the Trás-os-Montes and Alto Douro Cria multimunicipal water supply and sanitation system for the catchment, treatment and distribution of water for public consumption and the collection, treatment and rejection of effluents from the Alfândega da Fé, Alijó, Armamar, Boticas, Bragança, Chaves, Freixo de Espada à Cinta, Lamego, Macedo de Cavaleiros, Mesão Frio, Mirandela, Mogadouro, Moimenta da Beira, Montalegre, Murça, Peso da Régua, Resende, Ribeira de Pena, São João da Pesqueira, Sabrosa, Santa Marta de Penaguião, Sernancelhe, Tabuaço, Tarouca, Torre de Moncorvo, Valpaços, Vila Flor, Vila Nova de Foz Côa, Vila Pouca de Aguiar, Vila Real and Vinhais municipalities	DL_270-A_2001_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2001	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 288-A/2001	Sets up the Tejo and Trancão multimunicipal sanitation system for the collection, treatment and rejection of effluents from the Amadora, Lisboa, Loures, Mafra, Odivelas and Vila Franca de Xira municipalities	DL_288-A_2001_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2001	Declaração de Rectificação	Declaração de Rectificação n.º 20-AT/2001	Declares the rectification of Decree-Law No. 243/2001, which approves quality standards for drinking water, transposing into national law Directive 98/83/EC, relating to drinking water quality	DRec_20AT_2001_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2001	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 16/2001	Approves the Guadiana hydrographic basin plan	DR_16_2001_WATER_Portugal.pdf

2001	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 17/2001	Approves the Minho hydrographic basin plan	DR_17_2001_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2001	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 18/2001	Approves the Tagus hydrographic basin plan	DR_18_2001_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2001	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 19/2001	Approves the Douro hydrographic basin plan	DR_19_2001_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2001	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 130/2001	Determines the elaboration of the Aguieira Reservoir Land Use Plan and sets its respective coordination commission	RCM_130_2001_Water_Portugal.pdf
2001	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 131/2001	Determines the elaboration of the Crestuma-Lever Reservoir Land Use Plan and sets its respective coordination commission	RCM_131_2001_Water_Portugal.pdf
2001	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 132/2001	Determines the elaboration of the Tapada Grande Reservoir Land Use Plan and sets its respective coordination commission	RCM_132_2001_Water_Portugal.pdf
2001	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 133/2001	Determines the elaboration of the Cova do Viriato Reservoir Land Use Plan and sets its respective coordination commission	RCM_133_2001_Water_Portugal.pdf
2001	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 134/2001	Determines the elaboration of the Sabugal Reservoir Land Use Plan and sets its respective coordination commission	RCM_134_2001_Water_Portugal.pdf
2001	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 135/2001	Determines the elaboration of the Magos Reservoir Land Use Plan and sets its respective coordination commission	RCM_135_2001_Water_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 3/2002	Classifies a set of public water reservoirs as protected or free-use reservoirs, which must be subject to land use planning (in accordance with Regulatory Decree No. 2/88, with alterations introduced by Regulatory Decree No. 37/91)	DR_3_2002_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 5/2002	Approves the Mira hydrographic basin plan	DR_5_2002_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 6/2002	Approves the Sado hydrographic basin plan	DR_6_2002_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 9/2002	Approves the Mondego hydrographic basin plan	DR_9_2002_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 11/2002	Approves the Lima hydrographic basin plan	DR_11_2002_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 12/2002	Approves the Ribeiras do Algarve hydrographic basin plan	DR_12_2002_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 15/2002	Approves the Vouga hydrographic basin plan	DR_15_2002_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 17/2002	Approves the Cávado hydrographic basin plan	DR_17_2002_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 18/2002	Approves the Leça hydrographic basin plan	DR_18_2002_WATER_Portugal.pdf

2002	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 19/2002	Approves the Ave hydrographic basin plan	DR_19_2002_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 23/2002	Approves the Lis hydrographic basin plan	DR_23_2002_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 26/2002	Approves the Ribeiras do Oeste hydrographic basin plan	DR_26_2002_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2002	Despacho conjunto	Despacho Conjunto n.º 299/2002 (Série II)	Determines a list making of presses permitted to work at the start of each annual campaign, in accordance with its conforming to legislation in demesrial water usage	DC_299_2002_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 112/2002	Approves the National Water Plan (PNA), which is aimed at establishing in a structured and programmed manner a rational plan for the management and use of all national water resources, in conjunction with land use planning and environmental conservation and protection. To this end, the National Water Plan (PNA) is based on the various already approved hydrographic basin plans, synthesising and systematising the respective diagnostics, linking and prioritising identified objectives, proposing measures for the coordination of the PBH and establishing a concrete, financial and institutional plan for actions to implement	DL_112_2002_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 130/2002	Sets up the Centro Alentejo multinational water supply and sanitation system for the catchment, treatment and distribution of water for public consumption and the collection, treatment and rejection of effluents from the Alandroal, Borba, Évora, Mourão, Redondo and Reguengos de Monsaraz municipalities	DL_130_2002_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 135/2002	Sets up the Vale do Ave multinational water supply and sanitation system for the catchment, treatment and distribution of water for public consumption and the collection, treatment and rejection of effluents from the Fafe, Guimarães, Póvoa de Lanhoso, Santo Tirso, Trofa, Vieira do Minho, Vila Nova de Famalicão and Vizela municipalities, and constitutes the system's concessionary company	DL_135_2002_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 151/2002	Alters the Regulatory Institute of Water and Waste Water (IRAR), approved by Decree-Law No. 362/98, establishing that IRAR starts to implement monitoring and inspection actions with relation to water quality in all public supply sites, and has the responsibility to alert health authorities and the	DL_151_2002_WATER_Portugal.pdf

			managing body as to possible occurrences of irregularities and undertakes to elaborate yearly technical reports on the quality of drinking water, with a view to reporting back to the public, as well as tri-annual reports on the quality of drinking water. Establishes that working costs of IRAR should be borne by all multimunicipal and municipal systems that manage public water supplies	
2002	Despacho	Despacho n.º 22440/2002 (Série II)	Determines the setting up of a work group to elaborate the project for the water framework Bill	Desp_22440_2002_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 268/2002	Repeals No 4 of Article 7 of Decree-Law No 156/98, which establishes regulations relating to the recognition of natural mineral water and the characteristics and conditions to observe in the treatment, labelling and marketing of natural mineral water and spring water	DL_268_2002_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2002	<i>Resolução do Conselho de Ministros</i>	<i>Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 45/2002</i>	Approves the Cabril, Bouça and Santa Luzia Reservoirs Land Use Plan	RCM_45_2002_Water_Portugal.pdf
2002	<i>Resolução do Conselho de Ministros</i>	<i>Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 62/2002</i>	Approves the Régua and Carrapateiro Reservoirs Land Use Plan	RCM_62_2002_Water_Portugal.pdf
2002	<i>Resolução do Conselho de Ministros</i>	<i>Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 92/2002</i>	Approves the revision of the Caniçada Reservoir Land Use Plan	RCM_92_2002_Water_Portugal.pdf
2002	<i>Resolução do Conselho de Ministros</i>	<i>Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 94/2002</i>	Approves the Montargil Reservoir Land Use Plan (POAM)	RCM_94_2002_Water_Portugal.pdf
2002	<i>Resolução do Conselho de Ministros</i>	<i>Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 95/2002</i>	Approves the Alqueva and Pedrógão Reservoirs Land Use Plan (POAAP)	RCM_95_2002_Water_Portugal.pdf
2002	<i>Resolução do Conselho de Ministros</i>	<i>Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 139/2002</i>	Determines the elaboration of the Odelouca Reservoir Land Use Plan and sets its respective coordination commission	RCM_139_2002_Water_Portugal.pdf
2002	<i>Resolução do Conselho de Ministros</i>	<i>Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 140/2002</i>	Determines the elaboration of the Tapada Pequena Reservoir Land Use Plan and sets its respective coordination commission	RCM_140_2002_Water_Portugal.pdf
2003	Despacho Normativo	Despacho Normativo n.º 14/2003	Approves the minimum technical standards that must be met for the elaboration of specific plans for the management of the extraction of inert matter in demersal water	DN_14_2003_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2003	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 69/2003	Approves the revision of the Castelo do Bode Reservoir Land Use Plan	RCM_69_2003_WATER_Portugal.pdf

2003	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 97/2003	Establishes the structure of the Ministry of Cities, Land Use Planning and the Environment (MCOTA)	DL_97_2003_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2003	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 103/2003	Adds Article No. 4-A to Decree-Law No. 379/93, which establishes the regime for the exploration and management of multimunicipal and municipal systems of catchment, treatment and distribution of water for public consumption, the collection, treatment and rejection of effluents and the collection and treatment of solid waste	DL_103_2003_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2003	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 222/2003	Adds Article No. 6 to Decree-Law No. 319/94, which establishes the legal regime of the construction, exploitation and management of multimunicipal systems of catchment of water for public consumption	DL_222_2003_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2003	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 223/2003	Adds Article No. 7 of Decree-Law No. 162/96, which establishes the legal regime of the construction, exploitation and management of multimunicipal systems of collection, treatment and rejection of effluents	DL_223_2003_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2003	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1216/2003	Establishes criteria of responsibility sharing for the management and exploitation of a system of public supply of drinking water under the responsibility of two or more management bodies	P_1216_2003_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2003	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 261/2003	Alters the annex to Decree-Law No. 506/99, which sets quality goals in the water environment for certain hazardous substances included in the families and groups of substances on list II of Annex XIX of Decree-Law No. 236/98	DL_261_2003_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2003	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 284/2003	Prevention of pollution by ships that call at EU ports or sail in waters under the jurisdiction of the Member States	DL_284_2003_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2003	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 120/2003	Approves the Monte Novo Reservoir Land Use Plan	RCM_120_2003_Water_Portugal.pdf
2003	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 154/2003	Approves the Monte da Rocha Reservoir Land Use Plan	RCM_154_2003_Water_Portugal.pdf
2003	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 188/2003	Approves the Apartadura Reservoir Land Use Plan	RCM_188_2003_Water_Portugal.pdf
2004	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 149/2004	Alters Decree-Law No. 152/97, of 19 June, which transposes into national law Directive 91/271/EC, of the Council, of 21 May, concerning urban waste treatments	DL_149_2004_WATER_Portugal.pdf

2004	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 172/2004	Sets up a multimunicipal system for water supply and sanitation for Baixo Mondego-Bairrada and sets up the Mondego Water Society – the Baixo Mondego-Bairrada, S.A. Multimunicipal System of Water Supply and Sanitation	DL_172_2004_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2004	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 27/2004	Approves the Touvedo and Alto Lindoso Reservoirs Land Use Plan	RCM_27_2004_Water_Portugal.pdf
2004	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 42/2004	Approves the Cova do Viriato Reservoir Land Use Plan	RCM_42_2004_Water_Portugal.pdf
2004	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 71/2004	Approves the Bravura Reservoir Land Use Plan	RCM_71_2004_Water_Portugal.pdf
2004	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 158/2004	Approves the Vilar Reservoir Land Use Plan	RCM_158_2004_Water_Portugal.pdf
2005	Portaria	Portaria n.º 50/2005	Approves the programmes to reduce and control certain hazardous substances in water	P_50_2005_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2005	Portaria	Portaria n.º 284/2005	Sets the parameters for the protection of natural mineral water that corresponds to registration No. HM-41 and designation «Termas de São Vicente»	P_284_2005_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2005	Portaria	Portaria n.º 285/2005	Sets the parameters for the protection of natural mineral water that corresponds to registration No. HM-32 and designation «Caldas de Moledo»	P_285_2005_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2005	Portaria	Portaria n.º 286/2005	Sets the parameters for the protection of natural mineral water that corresponds to registration No. HM-3 and designation «Fonte Santa de Almeida»	P_286_2005_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2005	Portaria	Portaria n.º 289/2005	Sets the parameters for the protection of natural mineral water that corresponds to registration No. HM-21 and designation «Caldas do Carlão»	P_289_2005_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2005	Portaria	Portaria n.º 290/2005	Sets the parameters for the protection of natural mineral water that corresponds to registration No. HM-47 and designation «Termas do Vale da Mó»	P_290_2005_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2005	Portaria	Portaria n.º 291/2005	Sets the parameters for the protection of natural mineral water that corresponds to registration No. HM-46 and designation «Caldas do Cró»	P_291_2005_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2005	Portaria	Portaria n.º 292/2005	Sets the parameters for the protection of natural mineral water that corresponds to registration No. HM-35 and designation «Caldas de São Jorge»	P_292_2005_WATER_Portugal.pdf

2005	Declaração de rectificação	Declaração de rectificação 35/2005	Declares rectification of Ordinance (<i>Portaria</i>) No. 284/2005, which sets the parameters for the protection of natural mineral water that corresponds to registration No. HM-41 and designation «Termas de São Vicente»	DRec_35_2005_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2005	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 131/2005	Approves an exceptional and transitory regime of issuing licenses for the research into and the catchment of subterranean water and the installation of new surface water catchments for public supply and defines the minimum criteria needed to check water quality both at its source as well as its distribution for human consumption	DL_131_2005_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2005	Portaria	Portaria n.º 813/2005	Updates rates to be paid to IRAR (Water and Waste Regulatory Institute) by concessionary management bodies of multimunicipal and municipal systems of water for public consumption, urban water waste and urban solid waste	P_813_2005_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2005	Lei	Lei n.º 54/2005 de 15 Novembro	Establishes that water resources (water, waterbeds, banks, adjacent areas and maximum infiltration areas and protected areas), according to ownership, encompass domain resources or those belonging to public domain, and heritage resources, belonging to public or private entities	L_54_2005_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2005	Lei	Lei n.º 58/2005 de 29-12-2005	Approves the Water Framework Directive of the European Parliament of the Council, transposing into national law Directive 2000/60/EC of 23/10/2000, and establishes the bases and institutional framework for the sustainable management of water. Sets up the Hydrographic Regions Administration (ARH)	L_58_2005_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2005	Despacho	Despacho n.º 19213/2005 (II Série)	Sets up the work group for the elaboration of the new Strategic Plan for Water Supply and Waste Water Sanitation (PEAASAR II), for 2006-2013	Desp_19213_2005_Water_Portugal.pdf
2005	Despacho	Despacho n.º 23099/2005 (II Série)	Establishes a consultative council to accompany the elaboration of the new Strategic Plan for Water Supply and Waste Water Sanitation (PEAASAR II)	Desp_23099_2005_Water_Portugal.pdf
2005	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 35/2005	Approves the Pego do Altar Reservoir Land Use Plan	RCM_35_2005_Water_Portugal.pdf
2005	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 106/2005	Determines the revision of the Alvito reservoir Land Use Plan (approved by Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 151/1998)	RCM_106_2005_Water_Portugal.pdf

2005	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 107/2005	Approves the Santa Águeda and Pisco Reservoir Land Use Plan and the alteration of the demarcation of the National Ecological Reserve of the Castelo Branco and Fundão municipalities	RCM_107_2005_Water_Portugal.pdf
2005	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 113/2005	Approves the National Programme for the Efficient Use of Water – Bases and Guidelines (<i>PNUEA</i>).	RCM_113_2005_WATER_Portugal.pdf
2005	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 114/2005	Approves the Tapada Grande Reservoir Land Use Plan and the alteration of the National Ecological Reserve of Mértola municipality	RCM_114_2005_Water_Portugal.pdf
2005	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 115/2005	Approves the Divor Reservoir Land Use Plan, the alteration of the National Ecological Reserve of Arraiolos council and the partial demarcation of the National Ecological Reserve of Évora council, in the area included within the special plan	RCM_115_2005_Water_Portugal.pdf

Environmental Policy, Part 3: Nature Conservation

<i>Year</i>	<i>Type of legislation</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Objective</i>	<i>Data supplied</i>
1976	Portaria	Portaria n.º 89/76	Rewords No.1 of Ordinance (<i>Portaria</i>) No. 782/75, on professional net fishing licenses on a stretch of the River Alva	P_89_76_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1976	Despacho da Presidência do Conselho de Ministros	Despacho da Presidência do Conselho de Ministros, de 20-03-1976	Sets up the Portuguese Bird Ringing Centre (CEMPA)	DPCM_20_03_1976_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.doc
1976	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 378/76	Establishes conditions for the use of polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) with negative impacts in wildlife (mainly birds and fishes)	DL_378_76_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1976	Decreto	Decreto n.º 388/76	Sets up the Almada Landscape Reserve	D_388_76_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1976	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 557/76	Sets up the Serra da Estrela Natural Park	DL_557_76_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1976	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 565/76	Sets up the Tagus Estuary Nature Reserve	DL_565_76_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1976	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 613/76	Establishes the new regime for the protection of nature and creation of parks and creates the National Parks, Reserves and Landscape Heritage Service (SNPRPP)	DL_613_76_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1976	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 622/76	Sets up the Arrábida Natural Park	DL_622_76_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1976	Portaria	Portaria n.º 689/76	Forms a preparatory commission to start on the management of the Almada Landscape Reserve	P_689_76_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1977	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 14/77	Determines the provisions relating to removing, cutting and pruning holm oak trees	DL_14_77_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1977	Portaria	Portaria n.º 172/77	Sets up a interdisciplinary working group to study urban and regional planning and regulations of the Tagus Estuary Nature Reserve	P_172_77_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1977	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 487/77	Introduces alterations to Decree-Law No. 565/76, which sets up the Tagus Estuary Nature Reserve	DL_487_77_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1977	Portaria	Portaria n.º 727/77	Alters paragraph e) of Article 13 of Artisanal Fishing Regulation	P_727_77_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1978	Decreto	Decreto n.º 4/78	Defines the structure of nature parks, reserves and protected landscape	D_4_78_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf

1978	Decreto	Decreto n.º 37/78	Alters No. 1 of Article 3 of Decree No. 4/78, on the organization of parks, reserves and other protected areas	D_37_78_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1978	Portaria	Portaria n.º 241-C/78	Prohibits professional net fishing along the River Tâmega length between the river mouth and Lugar do Vau	P_241-C_78_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1978	Portaria	Portaria n.º 337/78	Approves regulations for the Sapal de Castro Marim Nature Reserve	P_337_78_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1978	Decreto	Decreto 45/78	Sets up the Ria Formosa Nature Reserve	D_45_78_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1978	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 221/78	Approves regulations for the protection of cork oak open forests	DL_221_78_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1978	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 29/78	Alters the wording of Articles 3 and 4 of Decree 45/78, which sets up the Ria Formosa Nature Reserve	DR_29_78_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1978	Portaria	Portaria n.º 595/78	Sets up a permanent protected area for game species along a strip of land close to the cliffs on the Mafra council coastline	P_595_78_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1978	Portaria	Portaria n.º 603/78	Sets up two permanent protected areas for game species along the cliffs on the Sintra council coastline	P_603_78_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1978	Portaria	Portaria n.º 647/78	Alters the Ordinance (<i>Portaria</i>) No. 337/78, which sets up the Sapal Castro Marim Nature Reserve	P_647_78_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1978	Portaria	Portaria n.º 658/78	Alters the Ordinance (<i>Portaria</i>) No.727/77, which sets the areas of shrimp and small crab (Pelagic Crab) nets in certain coastal areas nets	P_658_78_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1978	Portaria	Portaria n.º 774/78	Regulates and determines trout fishing zones	P_774_78_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1978	Despacho	Despacho, Conjunto (2.ª Série, Diário da República, n.º 291 de 1978)	Introduces alterations to the composition of the General Council of the Sapal de Castro Marim Nature Reserve in Vila Real de Santo António	Hardcopy_DC_291_1978_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal
1979	Portaria	Portaria n.º 36/79	Regulates fishing in reserved fishing zones in the hydrographic basin of the River Lima encompassing several watercourses	P_36_79_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1979	Portaria	Portaria n.º 41/79	Authorises licensed foreign fishing vessels to fish in the Portugal's Exclusive Economic Zone	P_41_79_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1979	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 40/79	Rewords Articles 1 and 5 of Decree-Law No. 613/76 on the competencies of the National Parks, Reserves and Protected Landscape Service	DL_40_79_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf

1979	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 41/79	Sets up the Dunas de São Jacinto Nature Reserve	DL_41_79_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1979	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 108/79	Defines and sets up Monte de S. Bartolomeu as a listed area	DL_108_79_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1979	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 16/79	Alters the Preparatory Commission of the Ria Formosa Nature Reserve	DR_16_79_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1979	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 118/79	Sets up the Serras de Aire and Candeeiros Natural Park	DL_118_79_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1979	Portaria	Portaria n.º 151/79	Determines a time period for the protection of trout fishing	P_151_79_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1979	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 140/79	Classifies the grotto at Zambujal and demarcates its protection zone	DL_140_79_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1979	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 167/79	Sets the limits of the Serra da Estrela Natural Park	DL_167_79_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1979	Decreto	Decreto n.º 49/79	Approves the Convention concerning the Protection of World Cultural and Natural Heritage	D_49_79_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1979	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 264/79	Ornithological refuges and areas to recover	DL_264_79_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1979	Portaria	Portaria n.º 409/79	Approves the General Regulations of the Serra da Estrela Natural Park	P_409_79_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1979	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 355/79	Sets up the Montesinho Natural Park	DL_355_79_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1979	Portaria	Portaria n.º 481/79	Approves the General Regulations of the Tagus Estuary Nature Reserve	P_481_79_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1979	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 519-C/79	Approves the Peneda-Gerês National Park Organic Law	DL_519-C_79_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1980	Portaria	Portaria n.º 26-F/80	Approves the Arrábida Natural Park Regulations	P_26-F_80_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1980	Despacho Normativo	Despacho Normativo n.º 96/80	Determines the maximum quantity of bivalve molluscs that each person can harvest a day	DN_96_80_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1980	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 55/80	Alters the wording of No. 2 of Article 11 of Decree-Law No. 41/79, which sets up the Dunas de São Jacinto Nature Reserve	DL_55_80_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1980	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 11/80	Regulates the harvesting and exploitation of clams and other bivalve shellfish	DR_11_80_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf

1980	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 197/80	Classifies the Monte da Barca and Agolada weirs	DL_197_80_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1980	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 198/80	Sets up the Paúl do Boquilobo Partial Nature Reserve	DL_198_80_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1980	Portaria	Portaria n.º 352/80	Sets up a permanent protection zone for game species, from the Lourinha council boundary with Torres Vedras council until the Areia Branca site.	P_352_80_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1980	Decreto	Decreto n.º 50/80	Approves, for ratification, the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES)	D_50_80_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1980	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 327/80	Determines that the Government should provide control measures to prevent and detect forest fires, especially by means of plans, determining climatic causes, launching campaigns and setting security norms and preparing studies	DL_327_80_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1980	Despacho Normativo	Despacho Normativo n.º 319/80	Approves the programme for the reconversion and development of fishing in Ria Formosa	DN_319_80_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1980	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 430/80	Sets up the Sado Estuary Nature Reserve	DL_430_80_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1980	Despacho Normativo	Despacho Normativo n.º 322/80	Sado Estuary – norms for tourism development on the Troia peninsula so as not to damage nature reserves and landscape	DN_322_80_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1980	Decreto	Decreto n.º 101/80	Approves, for ratification, the Convention on Wetlands of International Importance, especially as Waterfowl Habitat for Aquatic Birds (RAMSAR)	D_101_80_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1980	Decreto	Decreto n.º 103/80	Approves, for ratification, the Convention on the Conservation of Migratory Species of Wild animals (BONA)	D_103_80_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1980	Aviso	Aviso de 14-11-1980	Makes known that Portugal's representative at Unesco deposited with the Secretary-General the instrument for ratification of the Convention on the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage	A_14_11_1980_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.doc
1980	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1094-D/80	Alters the wording of Articles 2, 27 and 41 of the Coastal Trawl Fishing Regulation, approved by Ordinance (<i>Portaria</i>) No. 49/73	P_1094-D_80_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1981	Lei	Lei n.º 10/81	Ratifies, with amendments, Decree-Law No. 327/80, on prevention and detection of forest fires	L_10_81_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1981	Portaria	Portaria n.º 137/81	Approves various models of logos of protected areas	P_137_81_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf

1981	Portaria	Portaria n.º 232/81	Approves the Tagus Estuary Nature Reserve logo	P_232_81_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1981	Portaria	Portaria n.º 604/81	Adopts measures aimed at the protection of tuna species	P_604_81_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1981	Decreto	Decreto n.º 95/81	Approves, for ratification, the Convention on the Conservation of European Wildlife and Natural Habitats (BERN)	D_95_81_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1981	Despacho Normativo	Despacho Normativo n.º 192/81	Establishes norms relating to preventing immature species from being captured	DN_192_81_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1981	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 263/81	The Marine Mammal Protection Regulation	DL_263_81_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1981	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 264/81	Sets up the Berlenga Nature Reserve	DL_264_81_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1981	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 292/81	Sets up the Sintra-Cascais Protected Landscape Area	DL_292_81_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1981	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 294/81	Sets up the Serra da Malcata Partial Nature Reserve	DL_294_81_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1981	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 55/81	Regulates Decree-Law No. 327/80, in which the Government wants to promote the organisation of the prevention of Portugal's forest heritage	DR_55_81_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1982	Despacho Normativo	Despacho Normativo n.º 16/82	Clarifies doubts as to the interpretation of some legal dispositions in Decree-Law No. 292/81, which sets up the Sintra-Cascais Protected Landscape Area	DN_16_82_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1982	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 67/82	Sets up the Serra do Açor Protected Landscape Area	DL_67_82_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1982	Portaria	Portaria n.º 323/82	Prohibits, for two years, the fishing and catching of crayfish (<i>Astacus Pallipes</i>) in all dams in Portugal	P_323_82_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1983	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 49/83	Approves the Organic Law of the Ministry of the Quality of Life and sets up the National Service of Parks, Reserves and Nature Conservation (SNPRCN)	DL_49_83_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1983	Portaria	Portaria n.º 166/83	Regulates the workings of the National Commission for Fishing and Protection of Water Resources and Environment (CNAPRA)	P_166_83_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf

1983	Portaria	Portaria n.º 669-A/83	Regulates coastal trawl fishing (Alters some articles of Ordinance [<i>Portaria</i>] No. 49/73)	P_669-A_83_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1983	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 237/83	Sets up the Alvão Natural Park	DL_237_83_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1983	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 321/83	Sets up the National Ecological Reserve	DL_321_83_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1983	Portaria	Portaria n.º 826/83	Alters the wording of Article 27 of Ordinance (<i>Portaria</i>) No. 49/73 of the Coastal Trawl Fishing Regulation	P_826_83_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1983	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 390/83	Widens the composition of the Alvão Natural Park preparatory commission	DL_390_83_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1984	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 107/84	Alters the new drafting of the body and paragraph c) of Article 13 and adds Article 13–A to Decree-Law No. 49/83, which sets up the Organic Law of the National Parks, Reserves and Nature Conservation Service	DL_107_84_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1984	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 168/84.	Sets up the Arriba Fossil de Costa da Caparica Protected Landscape	DL_168_84_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1984	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 219/84	Establishes measures to be taken as to the implementation of the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES), approved, for ratification, by Decree No. 50/80, of 23 July	DL_219_84_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1984	Decreto do Governo	Decreto do Governo n.º 33/84	Approves, for adhesion, the additional Protocol in Paris, 1972, to the Ramsar Convention	DG_33_84_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1984	Portaria	Portaria n.º 691/84	Establishes the protected habitats zone along the Portuguese rocky coast (game species)	P_691_84_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1985	Portaria	Portaria n.º 397/85	Prohibits, until judged appropriate, fishing of and catching crayfish (<i>Astacus pallipes</i>) in all dams in Portugal	P_397_85_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1985	Portaria	Portaria n.º 615/85	Sets the closed season period of time for the protection of trout in certain lagoons	P_615_85_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1985	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 403/85	Determines that the management of the Peneda-Gerês National Park be transferred to the National Parks, Reserves and Nature Conservation Service	DL_403_85_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1986	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 3/86	Establishes the structure of the National Parks, Reserves and Nature Conservation Service (SNPRCN), set up by Decree-Law No. 49/83	DR_3_86_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1986	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 18/86	Alters the drafting of the body of Article 33 of Decree 312/70 and paragraph a) of Article 73, on fishing for crayfish in interior waterways	DR_18_86_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf

1986	Lei	Lei n.º 13/86	Decreases the aid the Regional Government of Madeira should give to protect the Selvagem Islands as a nature reserve	L_13_86_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1986	Lei	Lei n.º 30/86	Hunting Law - including elements relating to the conservation of game animals	L_30_86_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pt
1986	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 120/86	Establishes the provisions for conditions required to remove olive trees	DL_120_86_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1986	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 126/86	Repeals Decree-Law No. 403/85, of 14 October, which determines that management of the National Peneda-Gerês Park be transferred to the National Parks, Reserves and Nature Conservation Service	DL_126_86_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1987	Portaria	Portaria n.º 27/87	Alters the Serra da Estrela Natural Park regulations	P_27_87_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1987	Portaria	Portaria n.º 51/87	Alters the Arrábida Natural Park regulations	P_51_87_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1987	Lei	Lei n.º 11/87	Basic Environmental Law, particularly the concepts, definitions and general principles relating to Nature Conservation	L_11_97_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1987	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 230/87	Establishes preventive and cautionary measures for the area of the lagoon Albufeira (Sesimbra)	DL_230_1987_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1987	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 278/87	Sets the legal regulatory framework for fishing and marine cultures	DL_278_87_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1987	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 43/87	Defines national conservation measures for the conservation of biological resources applicable to fishing in the open sea and interior waterways under Portugal's sovereignty and jurisdiction	DR_43_87_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1987	Declaração	Declaração de 31-08-1987	Rectifies Regulatory Decree No. 43/87, which defines national measures for the conservation of biological resources applicable to fishing in the open sea and interior waterways under Portugal's sovereignty and jurisdiction	Decl_31_08_87_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.doc
1987	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 311/87	Sets the legal regulatory framework for Hunting (Lei n.º 30/86)	DL_311_87_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1987	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 357/87	Sets up the Esposende Protected Coastal Landscape (APP)	DL_357_87_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1987	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 373/87	Sets up the Ria Formosa Natural Park (reclassifies the protected area set up by the Decree)	DL_373_87_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1988	Portaria	Portaria n.º 21/88	Approves the Serras de Aire and Candeeiros Natural Park regulations and the respective land use plan	P_21_88_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1988	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 219/88	Sets up the Paúl de Arzila Nature Reserve	DL_219_88_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf

1988	Portaria	Portaria n.º 163/88	Fisheries – prohibits certain bivalve mollusc fishing	P_163_88_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1988	Portaria	Portaria n.º 223/88	Authorises the catching of Red Swamp Crayfish (<i>Procambarus clarkii</i> Girard)	P_223_88_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1988	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 139/88	Establishes measures for land use planning areas that have suffered forest fires and lays down conditions for reforestation	DL_139_88_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1988	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 172/88	Prohibits the cutting or removal of holm oaks and determines that their trunk circumference must be marked beforehand	DL_172_88_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1988	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 241/88	Sets up the Southwest Alentejo and Vicentine Coast Natural Landscape Protected Area	DL_241_88_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1988	Decreto	Decreto n.º 17/88	Approves, for ratification, an amendment to the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES)	D_17_88_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1988	Decreto	Decreto n.º 30/88	Approves Fishing Regulations for border stretches of rivers between Portugal and Spain, with the exception of the River Minho and the zone under the River Guadiana maritime jurisdiction	D_30_88_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1988	Decreto	Decreto-Lei n.º 274-A/88	Sets the legal regulatory framework for Hunting (Lei n.º 30/86), with amendments to Decreto-Lei n.º 311/87. Lists the hunting game species and prohibits the hunting of other species	DL_274-A_88_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1988	Lei	Lei n.º 90/88	Establishes the regulations for the protection of the Iberian wolf	L_90_88_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1988	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 34/88	Publishes the Organic Law of the National Institute of Investigation for Fisheries	DR_34_88_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1989	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 3/89	Alters the Regulatory Decree No. 43/87, of 17 July, relating to the typology of fishing techniques, fishing areas, vessel characteristics and fish sizes	DR_3_89_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1989	Portaria	Portaria n.º 79/89	Establishes that the Choupal National Forest be managed by the National Parks, Reserves and Nature Conservation Service	P_79_89_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1989	Resolução da Assembleia da República	Resolução da Assembleia da República n.º 10/89	Approves, for adhesion, the Conventions that sets up the International Union for the Conservation of Nature and its resources	RAR_10_89_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1989	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 121/89	Sets up the Serra de São Mamede Natural Park	DL_121_89_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf

1989	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 11/89	Ends the closed season protection period for the Red Swamp Crayfish	DR_11_89_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1989	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 180/89	Regulates reforestation actions in protected areas affected by forest fires	DL_180_89_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1989	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 293/89	Alters Decree-Law No. 264/81, which sets up the Berlenga Nature Reserve	DL_293_89_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1989	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 316/89	Regulates the application of the Convention on the Conservation of European Wildlife and Natural Habitats	DL_316_89_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1989	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 423/89	Regime to protect holly (<i>azevinho espontâneo</i>)	DL_423_89_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1989	Portaria	Portaria n.º 957/89	Prohibits hunting in some areas of the Sado Estuary Nature Reserve	P_957_89_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1990	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 93/90	Reviews the legal regime established by Decree-Law No. 321/83, which sets up the National Ecological Reserve (REN), and creates the National Ecological Reserve Commission	DL_93_90_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1990	Decreto	Decreto n.º 114/90	Promotes the application of the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora	DL_114_90_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1990	Portaria	Portaria n.º 270/90	Determines that the number of people at the Berlenga Nature Reserve must not exceed 350 while characteristics currently prevalent in this protected area are checked	P_270_90_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1990	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei 139/90	Expands on the legal regime instituted by Law No. 90/88, of 13 August, on protection of the Iberian wolf	DL_139_90_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1990	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei 196/90	Alters Decree-Law No. 316/89, of 22 September, which regulates the Convention on the Conservation of European Wildlife and Natural Habitats	DL_196_90_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1990	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei 204/90	Establishes measures for the protection of necrophagous and predatory wild animals	DL_204_90_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1990	Portaria	Portaria n.º 560/90	Regulates fishing on Ria Formosa (seacoast inlet)	P_560_90_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1990	Portaria	Portaria n.º 561/90	Approves regulations for fishing on the River Lima	P_561_90_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1990	Portaria	Portaria n.º 562/90	Approves regulations for fishing on the River Sado	P_562_90_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1990	Portaria	Portaria n.º 563/90	Approves regulations for fishing on the Ria Aveiro (Aveiro seacoast inlet)	P_563_90_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf

1990	Portaria	Portaria n.º 564/90	Approves regulations for fishing on the River Mondego	P_564_90_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1990	Portaria	Portaria n.º 565/90	Approves regulations for fishing on the River Cávado	P_565_90_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1990	Portaria	Portaria n.º 566/90	Approves regulations for fishing on São Martinho do Porto Bay	P_566_90_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1990	Portaria	Portaria n.º 567/90	Approves regulations for fishing on Lagoa de Óbidos	P_567_90_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1990	Portaria	Portaria n.º 568/90	Approves regulations for fishing on the River Douro	P_568_90_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1990	Portaria	Portaria n.º 569/90	Approves regulations for fishing on the non-ocean interior waterways of the River Tagus	P_569_90_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1990	Portaria	Portaria n.º 583/90	Approves land use planning for the Serra da Estrela Natural Park and repeals Ordinance (<i>Portaria</i>) No. 409/79	P_583_90_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1990	Portaria	Portaria n.º 761/90	Alters regulations relating to the protection of animals during international transport	P_761_90_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1990	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 28/90	Alters the Regulatory Decree No. 43/87, of 17 July, which defines national measures to take for the conservation of biological resources applicable to fishing in sea and interior waterways	DR_28_90_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1990	Portaria	Portaria n.º 813/90	Establishes mesh size and net size for surrounding nets hauled on board	P_813_90_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1990	Portaria	Portaria n.º 815/90	Establishes limitations to anchored gillnet fishing, especially in the demarcation of areas where this kind of fishing is forbidden	P_815_90_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1990	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei 316/90	Foresees that the Ministry of Environment and Natural Resources intervenes in the management of the National Ecological Reserve and alters Decree-Law No. 93/90	DL_316_90_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1990	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1054/90	Establishes fishing methods to catch the Red Swamp Crayfish (<i>Procambarus Clarkii</i> Girard)	P_1054_90_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1990	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 327/90	Regulates occupation of land that has suffered a forest fire	DL_327_90_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1990	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1162/90	Sets the rates that the National Parks, Reserves and Nature Conservation Service should charge for the application of the Convention on International Trade of Endangered Fauna and Flora Species	P_1162_90_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1990	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1191/90	Establishes the maximum number of common prawn (<i>Palaemon serratus</i>) licenses	P_1191_90_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf

1990	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1222/90	Regulates common prawn (<i>Palaemon serratus</i>) fishing in Portugal's Exclusive Economic Zone waters	P_1222_90_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1991	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 2/91	Approves Ria Formosa Natural Park land use plan and respective regulations	DR_2_91_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1991	Despacho normativo	Despacho normativo 15/91	Prohibits the importation of skins and products derived from the pups of harp seal and hooded seals, except when they result from traditional hunting by the Inuit people	DN_15_91_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1991	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 75/91	Establishes measures for the protection of wild birds in Portugal (Transposes Directive No. 79/409/EC and 80/122/EC)	DL_75_91_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1991	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 7/91	Sets up the Monte Novo do Roncão Ornithological Refuge	RCM_7_91_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1991	Portaria	Portaria n.º 236/91	Regulates international trade in endangered species of wild fauna and flora.	P_236_91_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1991	Portaria	Portaria n.º 278/91	Sets a closed season period for the protection of various sportfishing species	P_278_91_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1991	Decreto	Decreto n.º 34/91	Approves, for adhesion, several amendments to the Ramsar Convention	D_34_91_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1991	Portaria	Portaria n.º 410/91	Stipulates for 1991 a new closed season period for dredge-fishing of all species of bivalves	P_410_91_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1991	Portaria	Portaria n.º 432-A/91	Divides Portugal's coast into various zones in order to implement closed season periods for bivalve fishing	P_432-A_91_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1991	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 30/91	Extends the period to carry out necessary alterations required of fishing vessels and alters Regulatory Decree No. 43/87	DR_30_91_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1991	Despacho normativo	Despacho Normativo n.º 126/91	Regulates the way the National Ecological Reserve Commission (created by Decreto-Lei n.º 93/90) works	DN_126_91_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1991	Portaria	Portaria n.º 785/91	Regulates the catching of species to use as live bait	P_785_91_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1991	Lei	Lei n.º 54/91	Alters, for ratification, Decree-Law No. 327/90, which regulates the occupation of land that has suffered a forest fire	L_54_91_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1991	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 392/91	Sets up the Rocha da Pena and Fonte Benémola Protected Areas	DL_392_91_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1991	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 393/91	Sets up the Granja dos Serrões and de Negrais Protected Areas	DL_393_91_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf

1991	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 394/91	Sets up the Montes de Santa Olaia and Ferrestelo Protected Location	DL_394_91_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1992	Portaria	Portaria n.º 149/92	Approves dredge-fishing regulations	P_149_92_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1992	Aviso	Aviso n.º 74/92.	Makes known that Amendments to Annex 1 of the Convention on the European Wildlife and Natural Habitats entered into force	A_74_92_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1992	Portaria	Portaria n.º 739/92	Fisheries – Prohibits the use of surrounding nets to haul on board that have a mesh size smaller than 16mm for catching small pelagic fish (repeals Ordinance [<i>Portaria</i>] No. 813/90)	P_739_92_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1992	Portaria	Portaria n.º 359/1992 (Série II)	Establishes that the capture of wild animals listed in Annex II of the Cites Convention is prohibited	Hardcopy_P_359_1992_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal
1992	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 213/92	Alters Decree-Law No. 93/90, which sets up the National Ecological Reserve	DL_213_92_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1992	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1005/92	Approves technical norms for the protection of animals used for experimental and other scientific purposes	P_1005_92_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1992	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 251/92	Establishes the legal regime for the promotion, exploitation and conservation of game hunting resources	DL_251_92_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1992	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1243/92	Prohibits anchored gillnet fishing less than a quarter mile from the coast	P_1243_92_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1992	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1244/92	Extends until 31 December 1993 the period of validity of Ordinance (<i>Portaria</i>) No. 1191/90, which establishes a maximum number of shrimp fishing licenses	P_1244_92_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1993	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 19/93	Establishes norms relating to the National Protected Areas network (following Decreto-Lei 613/76 and Lei n.º 11/87)	DL_19_93_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1993	Aviso	Aviso n.º 66/93	Makes known that the regulations for border stretches of rivers between Portugal and Spain have come into force	A_66_93_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1993	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 187/93	Establishes the structure of the Ministry of the Environment and Natural Resources (MARN)	DL_187_93_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1993	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 193/93	Establishes the structure of the Nature Conservation Institute (ICN) which replaces the the National Service of Parks, Reserves and Nature Conservation (SNPRCN)	DL_193_93_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf

1993	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 224/93	Alters Decree-Law No. 75/91, of 14 February, which establishes measures for the protection of wild birds in Portugal	DL_224_93_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1993	Decreto	Decreto n.º 21/93	Approves, for ratification, the Convention on Biodiversity	D_21_93_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1993	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 28/93	Classifies as protected the Monte Fidalgo lagoon	DR_28_93_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1993	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 309/93	Regulates the elaboration and approval of the Coastal Zone Land Use Plans (POOC's)	DL_309_1993_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal
1993	Portaria	Portaria n.º 725-G/93	Prohibits hunting in several areas with Migrant Bird Species, including in the the Açude da Murta Special Protection Area (SPA)	P_725-G_93_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1993	Portaria	Portaria n.º 817/93	Prohibits hunting in the Tagus Estuary Nature Reserve area	P_817_93_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1993	Portaria	Portaria n.º 818/93	Prohibits hunting in some areas of the Serra da Estrela Natural Park	P_818_93_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1993	Portaria	Portaria n.º 819/93	Prohibits hunting in some areas of the Southwest Alentejo and Vicentine Coast Natural Park	P_819_93_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1993	Portaria	Portaria n.º 820/93	Prohibits hunting in the Sapal de Castro Marim and Vila Real de Santo António Nature Reserve	P_820_93_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1993	Portaria	Portaria n.º 821/93	Prohibits hunting in the Paul de Arzila Nature Reserve	P_821_93_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1993	Portaria	Portaria n.º 822/93	Prohibits hunting in the Berlenga Nature Reserve	P_822_93_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1993	Portaria	Portaria n.º 823/93	Prohibits hunting in the Ria Formosa Natural Park	P_823_93_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1993	Portaria	Portaria n.º 833/93	Prohibits hunting in the Arrábida Natural Park	P_833_93_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1993	Portaria	Portaria n.º 834/93	Prohibits hunting in the Alvão Natural Park	P_834_93_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1993	Portaria	Portaria n.º 835/93	Prohibits hunting in the São Mamede Natural Park	P_835_93_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1993	Portaria	Portaria n.º 836/93	Prohibits hunting in the Dunas de São Jacinto Nature Reserve	P_836_93_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1993	Portaria	Portaria n.º 837/93	Prohibits hunting in the Serra do Açor Protected Landscape Area	P_837_93_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf

1993	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 39/93	Extends the time period for carrying out necessary alterations required for fishing vessels	DR_39_93_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1993	Portaria	Portaria n.º 872/93	Prohibits hunting in some sensitive areas of the Peneda-Gerês National Park	P_872_93_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1993	Portaria	Portaria n.º 873/93	Prohibits hunting in the North Coast Natural Park	P_873_93_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1993	Portaria	Portaria n.º 874/93	Prohibits hunting in some areas of the Serra da Malcata Nature Reserve	P_874_93_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1993	Portaria	Portaria n.º 881/93	Prohibits hunting in the Paul do Boquilobo Nature Reserve	P_881_93_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1993	Portaria	Portaria n.º 882/93	Prohibits hunting in the Arriba Fossil de Costa da Caparica Protected Landscape	P_882_93_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1993	Portaria	Portaria n.º 916/93	Prohibits hunting in some areas of the Montesinho Natural Park	P_916_93_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1993	Portaria	Portaria n.º 917/93	Prohibits hunting in some areas of the Serra de Aire e dos Candeeiros Natural Park	P_917_93_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1993	Portaria	Portaria n.º 920/93	Prohibits hunting in some areas of the the Sintra Cascais Natural Park	P_920_93_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1993	Portaria	Portaria n.º 921/93	Broadens the area in the Sado Estuary Nature Reserve where hunting is prohibited	P_921_93_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1993	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1329/93	Extends the validity of Ordinance (<i>Portaria</i>) No. 1191/90, which regulates fishing with shrimp and small crab (Pelagic) nets	P_1329_93_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1994	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 8/94	Sets up the Sintra-Cascais Natural Park	DR_8_94_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1994	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 9/94	Approves the Sintra-Park Natural Park land use plan and respective regulations	DR_9_94_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1994	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 31/94	Establishes the conditions for the application of EEC Regulations n.s 2078/92 e 2079/92 e 2080/92, on aid regimes to agricultural production methods	DL_31_94_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1994	Aviso	Aviso n.º 143/94	Makes known that Portugal has deposited letters of ratification of the Convention framework on biodiversity	A_143_94_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1994	Portaria	Portaria n.º 296/94	Mesh net fishing – Updates national legislation in force relating to fishing zones and periods of prohibition	P_296_94_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf

1994	Portaria	Portaria n.º 576/94	Approves regulations of the regime of aid for the renewal and modernisation of the fishing fleet, within the ambit of the Economic Development of the Fishing Sector programme (PROPECSA)	P_576_94_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1994	Portaria	Portaria n.º 577/94	Approves regulations of the regime of aid for adjustments to fishing efforts, within the ambit of the Economic Development of the Fishing Sector – PROPECSA	P_577_94_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1994	Portaria	Portaria n.º 688/94	Establishes the general regime for the provision of aid, within the ambit of agri-environment measures set up in (EEC) Regulation No. 2078/92	P_688_94_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1994	Declaração de Rectificação	Declaração de Rectificação n.º 136/94	Makes known the ratification of Ordinance (<i>Portaria</i>) No. 577/94, which approves the regime of aid for adjustments in fishing efforts, within the ambit of the Economic Development of the Fishing Sector	Drec_136_94_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1994	Declaração de Rectificação	Declaração de Rectificação n.º 138/94	Makes known the ratification of Ordinance (<i>Portaria</i>) No. 576/94, of the Ministry of Sea, which approves the regulations of the regime of aid for the renewal and modernisation of the fishing fleet, within the ambit of the Economic Development of the Fishing Sector programme	Drec_138_94_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1994	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 280/94	Sets up the Tagus Estuary Special Protection Area (SPA)	DL_280_94_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1994	Portaria	Portaria n.º 698/94	Establishes the regime of aid for the extensification or maintenance of extensive traditional farming systems approved within the ambit of agri-environment measures set up by EEC Regulation No. 2078/92	P_698_94_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1994	Portaria	Portaria n.º 703/94	Establishes the regime of aid for the protection of the environment and maintenance of the countryside within the ambit of agri-environment measures set up by EEC Regulation No. 2078/92	P_703_94_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1994	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1135/94	Updates national legislation in force relating to prohibited fishing areas and periods, with alterations to Ordinance (<i>Portaria</i>) No. 296/94	P_1135_94_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1995	Portaria	Portaria n.º 415/95	Broadens the area in the Sintra Cascais Natural Park where hunting is prohibited	P_415_95_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1995	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1177/95	Establishes the application regime of the zonal programme in the Castro Verde (Corine Biotope)	P_1177_95_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1995	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1199/95	Broadens the area in the Montesinho Natural Park where hunting is prohibited	P_1199_95_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf

1995	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1336/95	Alters Ordinances (<i>Portarias</i>) Nos. 1059/95, 858/94, 698/94, 703/94 and 1177/95, which respectively establish the regime of aid to reduce and rationalise the application of phytopharmaceutical products, biological production methods, extension and/or maintenance of traditional extensive farming systems, conservation of rural resources and landscape and the Castro Verde zone programme	P_1336_95_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1995	Lei	Lei n.º 86/95	Agriculture Development Framework Law	L_86_95_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1995	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 79/95	Alters Decree-Law No. 93/90, which sets up the National Ecological Reserve	DL_79_95_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1995	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 38/95	Publishes the National Environment Policy Plan, which includes strategic guidelines for the conservation of nature	RCM_38_95_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1995	Decreto	Decreto n.º 24/95	Approves, for adhesion, the Agreement to Promote Compliance with International Conservation and Management Measures by Fishing Vessels on the High (Fisheries)	D_24_95_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1995	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 151/95	Harmonises the legal regime of Special Land Use Planning, including land use planning of Protected Areas	DL_151_95_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1995	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 218/95	Regulates motor vehicle use on beaches, dunes, cliffs and integral reserves	DL_218_95_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1995	Lei	Lei n.º 92/95	Animal Protection Law, which prohibits unjustified violence against animals and defines aspects as to trading in animals and using animals in performance venues, as well as the need to conserve the ecosystems of endangered animals	L_92_95_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1995	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 26/95	Sets up the Southwest Alentejo and Vicentine Coast Natural Park, which includes an adjacent marine area (reclassifies the previous Southwest Alentejo and Vicentine Coast Natural Landscape Protected Area, created by Decreto-Lei n.º 241/88)	DR_26_95_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1995	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 134/95	Approves the Peneda-Gerês National Park land use plan	RCM_134_95_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1995	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 28/95	Sets up the Vale do Guadiana Natural Park	DR_28_95_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1995	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 33/95	Approves the Southwest Alentejo and Vicentine Coast Natural Park Land Use Plan	DR_33_95_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1995	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1487/95	Approves regulations for the application of aid regimes for operational interventions of Community initiatives for fishing	P_1487_95_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf

1996	Lei	Lei n.º 5/96	Alters Decree-Law No. 151/95, which defines special land use planning as being plans relating to protected areas, public water lagoon plans and coastline plans	L_5_96_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1996	Portaria	Portaria n.º 152-A/96	Determines that it is of public and national interest to safeguard the Samouco saltpan habitat	P_152-A_96_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1996	Portaria	Portaria n.º 223/96	Sets the percentage of rates foreseen in Decree-Law No. 251/92 (establishes the legal regime for the promotion, exploitation and conservation of game hunting resources)	P_223_96_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1996	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 102/96	Determines that government departments should establish concrete measures for the sustainable development of protected areas, and that priority be given to the approval of economic development projects that lead to job creation in protected areas. Also determines priority and maximum co-participation levels should be provided to local authority's projects within the National Protected Areas network, within the ambit of the II Community Aid Framework programme	RCM_102_96_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1996	Portaria	Portaria n.º 236/96 (2.ª Série, 06/11/1996)	Redefines the areas in the Montesinho Natural Park where hunting is prohibited	Hardcopy_P_236_1996_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal
1996	Aviso	Aviso n.º 228/96	Makes known Amendments introduced to Annexes II and II of the Convention on Conservation of European Wildlife and Natural Habitats	A_228_96_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1996	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 136/96	Establishes the legal regime for the promotion, exploitation and conservation of game hunting resources, repealing Decree-Law No. 251/92	DL_136_96_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1996	Lei	Lei n.º 33/96	Publishes the Basic Law for Forestry Policy	L_33_96_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1996	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 169/96	Alters Decree-Law No. 193/93, which establishes the Organic Law of the Nature Conservation Institute (ICN), which is dependent on the Ministry of Environment	DL_169_96_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1996	Portaria	Portaria n.º 393/96	Alters Ordinance (<i>Portaria</i>) No. 688/94, on agri-environmental measures	P_393_96_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1996	Portaria	Portaria n.º 698-A/96	Repeals Ordinance (<i>Portaria</i>) No. 1135/94, which suspends fishing prohibitions as established in No. 1, paragraph a) and No. 2, paragraph a) of Ordinance (<i>Portaria</i>) No. 296/94	P_698-A_96_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1996	Portaria	Portaria n.º 767/96	Approves the technical reference standards to observe in the elaboration of the Coastal Zone Land Use Planning (POOC).	P_767_1996_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf

1997	Portaria	Portaria n.º 748/97 (2.ª Série, 30/09/1997)	New redefining of the areas in the Montesinho Natural Park where hunting is prohibited	Hardcopy_P_748_1997_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal
1997	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1036/97	Introduces changes to Portaria n.º 698/94 (agri-environmental measures) and to Portaria n.º 1177/95 (about Castro Verde Corine Biotope zonal programme)	P_1036_97_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1997	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 11/97	Approves the protection of cork oak and holm oak forests	DL_11_97_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1997	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 46/97	Establishes the Tagus Estuary Special Protection Area, set up by Decree-Law No. 280/94	DL_46_97_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1997	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 5-A/97	Establishes the reclassification of the Montesinho Natural Park, maintaining the previous statute	DR_5-A_97_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1997	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 213/97	Alters No. 2 of Article 17 and paragraph b) of No. 1 of Article 19 of Decree-Law No. 19/93, which establishes norms relating to the National Protected Areas network	DL_213_97_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1997	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 221/97	Sets up the National Environment and Sustainable Development Council	DL_221_97_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1997	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 226/97	Transposes Directive No. 92/43/EC, on the conservation of the natural habitats of wild flora and fauna	DL_226_97_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1997	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 142/97	Approves the Portuguese list of sites (1st phase), foreseen in Article 3 of Decree-Law No. 226/97	RCM_142_97_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1997	Decreto	Decreto n.º 59/97	Approves, for ratification, the Convention for the Protection of Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic	D_59_97_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1997	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 45/97	Establishes the reclassification of the Paúl de Arzila Nature Reserve, maintaining the previous statute	DR_45_97_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1997	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 46/97	Establishes the reclassification of the Dunas de São Jacinto Nature Reserve	DR_46_97_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1997	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 49/97	Establishes the reclassification of the Paúl do Boquilobo Nature Reserve	DR_49_97_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1997	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 50/97	Establishes the reclassification of the Serra da Estrela Natural Park	DR_50_97_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1997	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 327/97	Alters Decree-Law No. 280/94, on the Tagus Estuary Special Protection Area (ZPE)	DL_327_97_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf

1998	Portaria	Portaria n.º 85/98	Approves regulations on the application of the aid regime to agri-environment measures	P_85_98_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1998	Portaria	Portaria n.º 117/98	Sets rates for the Nature Conservation Institute to collect within the application of CITES	P_117_98_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1998	Aviso	Aviso n.º 63/98	Makes known that Amendments to Annexes I, II and III of the Convention on the Conservation of European Wildlife and Natural Habitats	A_63_98_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1998	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 8/98	Establishes the classification of the International Douro Natural Park	DR_8_98_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1998	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 73/98	Declares 28 July to be National Nature Conservation Day	RCM_73_98_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1998	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 112/98	Establishes the setting up of a National Nature Tourism Programme in the protected areas	RCM_112_98_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1998	Aviso	Aviso n.º 140/98	Makes known that Portugal deposited its instrument of ratification for the Convention on the Conservation of Migratory Species of Wild Animals	A_140_98_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1998	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 227/98	Alters Decree-Law No. 19/93 (norms relating to the National Protected Areas network)	DL_227_98_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1998	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 236/98	Establishes quality standards, criteria and aims with a view to protecting the aquatic environment and improving water quality to support aquicolous life (surface fresh water for aquicolous purposes - , fishing areas; coastal and salty waters for aquicolous purposes – shellfishing areas)	DL_236_98_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1998	Lei	Lei n.º 48/98	Establishes the framework policy on Land Use and Urban Planning (including principles and objectives on the sustainable use of natural resources)	L_48_98_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1998	Lei	Lei n.º 52/98	Alters the sole article of Decree-Law No. 327/97, which sets up the Tagus Estuary Special Protection Area	L_52_98_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1998	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 23/98	Establishes the reclassification of the Arrábida Natural Park, maintaining its statute but altering its demarcation to include a Marine Reserve area	DR_23_98_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1998	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 30/98	Establishes the reclassification of the Berlengas Nature Reserve, enlarging its area to cover all the archipelago of Berlengas, creating a broader Marine Reserve	DR_30_98_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf

1998	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 123/98	Approves the Coastal Zone Land Use Plan (POOC) for the Cidadela-Forte de São Julião da Barra stretch	RCM_123_98_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1998	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 152/98	Approves the Sines-Burgau Coastal Zone Land Use Plan (POOC)	RCM_152_98_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1998	Declaração de Rectificação	Declaração de Rectificação n.º 22-H/98	Rectifies Council of Ministers Resolution No. 123/98, which approves the Coastal Zone Land Use Plan (POOC) for the Cidadela-Forte de São Julião da Barra stretch	DRec_22H_98_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1999	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 34/99	Alters Articles 1 and 2 of Decree-Law No. 327/90, which regulates occupation of land that has suffered a forest fire	DL_34_99_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1999	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 76/99	Repeals Decree-Law No. 327/97 and restores paragraph a) of No. 1 of Article 7 of the Decree-Law No. 280/94, which prohibits the licensing of new allotments in the Tagus Estuary Special Protection Area	DL_76_99_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1999	Aviso	<u>Aviso n.º 227/99</u>	Makes known the setting of the amendments to Annexes I, II of the Convention on the Conservation of Migratory Species of Wild animals (BONA) (approved for ratification by Decreto n.º 103/80)	A_227_99_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1999	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 25/99	Approves the Caminha-Espinho Coastal Zone Land Use Plan (POOC)	RCM_25_99_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1999	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 27/99	Adopts the Plan for the Sustainable Development of Portuguese Forests	RCM_27_99_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1999	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 33/99	Approves the Burgau-Vilamoura Coastal Zone Land Use Plan (POOC)	RCM_33_99_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1999	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 41/99	Sets up a interministerial commission aimed at ensuring the implementation of the Biodiversity Convention	RCM_41_99_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1999	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 140/99	Transposes Directive 79/409/EC on the conservation of wild birds (Birds Directive) and Directive 92/43/EC on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora (Habitats Directive)	DL_140_99_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1999	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 9/99	Alters Regulatory Decree No. 33/95, which approves the Southwest Alentejo and Vicentine Coast Natural Park land use plan	DR_9_99_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf

1999	Portaria	Portaria n° 486/99	Determines that 10 vessels should be licensed for dredge-fishing in the north-west area, demarcated to the north by the border of Portuguese territorial seas and the south by the parallel of “Pedrógão” (39° 55' 6" N.)	P_486_99_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1999	Portaria	Portaria n° 670-A/99, de 30 de Junho (2.ª Série)	Approves the Management Plan and respective regulations on the Tagus Estuary Special Protection Area (SPA)	P_670A_99_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.doc
1999	Portaria	Portaria n° 726/99	Prohibits hunting in the Fonte Benémola Protected area	P_726_99_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1999	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 11/99	Establishes setting up the Serra de Montejunto Protected Landscape (protected area within the regional ambit)	DR_11_99_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 13/99	Establishes setting up the Albufeira do Azibo Protected Landscape (protected area within the regional ambit)	DR_13_99_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1999	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 18/99	Regulates environmental edutainment, combining education with entertainment and fun activities, environmental information and nature sports in protected areas, as well as licensing project initiatives and activities, services and facilities for environmental edutainment	DR_18_99_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1999	Resolução da Assembleia da República	Resolução da Assembleia da República n.º 69/99	The Assembly of the Republic recommendation to the government that a possible redefinition of the Tagus Estuary Special Protection Area must be preceded by a hearing with local authorities involved, environmental protection organisations, the Nature Conservation Institute and the Tagus Estuary Special Protection Area bodies themselves	RAR_69_99_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1999	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 21/99	Sets up the Corno do Bico Protected Landscape	DR_21_99_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1999	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 204/99	Regulates processes related to Regional Forestry Plans (PROF), according to Law n.º 33/96 (article 5.º)	DL_204_1999_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1999	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 380/99	Defines the legal framework for the coordination and implementation of the Land Use and Urban Planning instruments (established in Law n.º 48/98)	DL_380_1999_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1999	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 384-B/99	Sets up several Special Protection Areas (ZPE) and reviews the transposition of Directives 79/409/EC and 92/43/EC into national law	DL_384-B_99_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1999	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 28/99	Establishes the reclassification of the Serra da Malcata Nature Reserve and redefines its demarcation area	DR_28_99_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf

1999	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 32/99	Alters Regulatory Decree No. 30/98 on the reclassification of the Berlengas Nature Reserve, allowing captures of <i>Pollicipes pollicipes</i> in quantities and seasons to establish	DR_32_99_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1999	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 565/99	Regulates the introduction of non-indigenous flora and fauna into nature, generally forbidding their intentional introduction in Portugal	DL_565_99_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1999	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1102/99	Regulates the 1999-2000 harvest of the European eel (<i>Anguilla anguilla</i>)	P_1102_99_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1999	Lei	Lei 173/99	General Framework Hunting Law - including elements related to Management of Game Hunting Resources	L_173_99_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
1999	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 136/99	Approves the Sado-Sines Coastal Zone Land Use Plan (POOC)	RCM_136_1999_Water_Portugal.pdf
2000	Acórdão	Acórdão n.º 95/2000	Constitutional Tribunal pronouncement on the popular referendum about the Corno de Bico Protected Area	ATC_95_2000_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2000	Aviso	Aviso n.º 5690/2000 (Série II)	Classifies watercourses as fishing waters in accordance with Article 33 of Decree-Law No. 236/98	A_5690_2000_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2000	Portaria	Portaria n.º 378/2000	Approves regulations for goose barnacles (<i>Pollicipes pollicipes</i>) harvesting in the Berlengas Nature Reserve area	P_378_2000_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2000	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 46/2000	Determines the revision of land use planning for the Sintra-Cascais Natural Park, approved by Regulatory Decree No. 9/94, and the setting up of preventive measures to be taken in some areas within the current land use planning	RCM_46_2000_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2000	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 76/2000	Approves the second phase of the national list of sites, to which No. 1 of Article 4 of Decree-Law No.140/99 refers (Habitats Directive)	RCM_76_2000_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2000	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 142/2000	Approves the Ovar-Marinha Grande Coastal Zone Land Use Plan (POOC)	RCM_142_2000_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2000	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 9/2000	Sets up the International Tagus Natural Park	DR_9_2000_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2000	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 10/2000	Sets up the Lagoa de Santo André and Lagoa de Sancha Nature Reserve, which includes the adjacent marine zone	DR_10_2000_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2000	Aviso	Aviso n.º 12677/2000 (Série II)	Repeals Advice No. 5690/2000 which classifies watercourses as fishing waters	A_12677_2000_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf

2000	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 227-B/2000	Establishes the Legal System for Sustainable Game Hunting Resources Management, including elements relating to the conservation of game animals and regulates Law No. 173/99 – General Framework Hunting Law	DL_227-B_2000_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2000	Portaria	Portaria n.º 744/2000	Prohibits hunting in some areas of the International Douro Natural Park	P_744_2000_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2000	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1102-D/2000	Approves regulations for pot fishing	P_1102-D_2000_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2000	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1102-E/2000	Approves regulations for seine net fishing	P_1102-E_2000_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2000	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1102-F/2000	Approves regulations for trawl net fishing (Xávega technique)	P_1102-F_2000_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2000	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1102-G/2000	Approves regulations for surround net fishing	P_1102-G_2000_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2000	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1102-H/2000	Approves regulations for gillnet fishing	P_1102-H_2000_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2000	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 19/2000	Sets up the Lagoa de Bertandos and Lagoa de São Pedro de Arcos Protected Landscape	DR_19_2000_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2000	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1226-GE/2000	Prohibits hunting in some areas of the Tagus Estuary SPA	P_1226-GE_2000_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2001	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 8/2001	Establishes the general rules of application of the Rural Development Plan (RURIS)	DL_8_2001_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2001	Portaria	Portaria n.º 27/2001	Sets minimum size of fish, crustaceans and molluscs to catch in the sea, maritime interior waters and non-maritime interior waters	P_27_2001_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2001	Portaria	Portaria n.º 44/2001	Establishes restrictions on dredge-fishing in the north-west area. Repeals Ordinance (<i>Portaria</i>) No. 386/2000	P_44_2001_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2001	Portaria	Portaria n.º 134/2001	Regulates the European eel 2000/2001 harvesting (Fisheries)	P_134_2001_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2001	Despacho-Normativo	Despacho-Normativo n.º 10/2001	Approves the regulation to apply the «Aquatic Resources Protection and Development» measure	DN_10_2001_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2001	Portaria	Portaria n.º 213/2001	Prohibits fishing with gillnets and trammel nets in the Beirinha zone	P_213_2001_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2001	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 169/2001	Establishes measures for the protection of cork oak and holm oak trees	DL_169_2001_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2001	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 202/2001	Alters Decree-Law No 8/200, that establishes general rules of application of the Rural Development Plan (RURIS)	DL_202_2001_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2001	Portaria	Portaria n.º 475/2001	Regulates de application of the of agri-environment intervention in the Rural Development Plan (RURIS)	P_475_2001_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf

2001	Portaria	Portaria n.º 543-D/2001	Establishes restrictions on bivalve fishing in the south-west zone, repealing Ordinances (<i>Portarias</i>) Nos. 194-A/2000 and 737/2000	P_543-D_2001_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2001	Despacho	Despacho n.º 11728/2001	Sets the number of authorised pickers/divers and vessels per zone for harvesting vegetable marine species	Desp_11728_2001_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2001	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 44/2001	Determines the elaboration of the Tagus Estuary Nature Reserve land use plan	RCM_44_2001_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2001	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 45/2001	Determines the elaboration of the Paúl de Arzila Nature Reserve land use plan	RCM_45_2001_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2001	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 46/2001	Determines the elaboration of the Paúl de Boquilo Partial Nature Reserve land use plan	RCM_46_2001_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2001	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 47/2001	Determines the elaboration of the Berlengas Nature Reserve land use plan	RCM_47_2001_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2001	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 48/2001	Determines the elaboration of the Serra da Malcata Nature Reserve land use plan	RCM_48_2001_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2001	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 49/2001	Determines the elaboration of the Dunas de São Jacino Nature Reserve land use plan	RCM_49_2001_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2001	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 66/2001	Determines the elaboration of a sectoral plan relating to the implementation of the Natura 2000 network (REDE NATURA 2000) and sets up a mixed coordination commission	RCM_66_2001_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2001	Despacho	Despacho n.º 18051/2001 (II Série)	Sets criteria and conditions for the licensing of floating net fishing [<i>pesca com majoeira</i>]	Desp_18051_2001_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2001	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 152/2001	Adopts a National Strategy for Nature and Biodiversity Conservation (ENCNB)	RCM_152_2001_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2001	Declaração de Rectificação	Declaração de Rectificação n.º 20-AG/2001	Makes known the ratification of Resolution No.152/2001, which adopts the national strategy for nature and biodiversity conservation	DRec_20-AG_2001_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2001	Portaria	Portaria n.º 281/2001	Prohibits hunting in the Lagoas de Santo André e da Sancha Nature Reserve area	P_281_2001_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf

2002	Portaria	Portaria n°71/2002	Prohibits hunting in some areas of the Vale do Guadiana Natural Park	P_71_2002_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2002	Portaria	Portaria n° 123-B/2002	Prohibits catching, keeping on board, landing and commercialising sardines between 15 February and 15 April 2002, north of latitude 39° 55' 4" N., and foresees financial support for ship owners and crews affected as a result of this biological pause	P_123-B_2002_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2002	Portaria	Portaria n° 402/2002	Alters the Annex to Ordinance (<i>Portaria</i>) No 27/2001, of 15 January, with reference to the minimum size of plaice, meagre and spiny lobster	P_402_2002_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 140/2002	Alters Decree-Law No. 280/94 and redefines the limits of the Tagus Estuary SPA, altering Decree-Laws Nos. 51/95 and 46/97	DL_140_2002_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 141/2002	Alters the demarcation of the International Tagus, the Erges and Ponsul, and the Moura, Mourão and Barrancos Special Protection Areas (SPA)	DL_141_2002_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2002	Portaria	Portaria n° 1072/2002	Sets restriction on dredge-fishing in the South Zone	P_1072_2002_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 203/2002	Alters Article 9 of the Decree-Law No. 93/90, on local authorities' participation with regard to new demarcations of the National Ecological Reserve	DL_203_2002_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 204/2002	Maintains in force classification for protected areas operated by diplomas that set them up or their respective classification	DL_204_2002_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2002	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 221/2002	Alters Decree-Law No.19/93, which establishes norms relating to the National Protected Areas network	DL_221_2002_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2002	Despacho	Despacho n.º 25297/2002 (2.ª Série)	Prohibits, with a view to protecting and improving the natural environment, abandoning or dumping any non-biodegradable waste in rural areas above or below ground or in watercourses	Desp_25297_2002_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2002	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 39/2002	Designates the Institute of the Environment (IA) to be responsible for the elaboration of the National Strategy for the Environment and Sustainable Development (ENDS)	RCM_39_2002_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2002	Portaria	Portaria n°1155/2002	Redefines the areas in the Serra de Aire e dos Candeeiros Natural Park where hunting is prohibited	P_1155_2002_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf

2002	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1250/2002	Redefines the areas in the International Douro Natural Park where hunting is prohibited	P_1250_2002_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2003	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 97/2003	Establishes the structure of the Ministry of Cities, Land Use Planning and the Environment (MCOTA)	DL_97_2003_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2003	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 22/2003	Approves the FINISTERRA Programme (Mainland Portugal Coastal Zone Intervention Programme)	RCM_22_2003_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2003	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 86/2003	Approves the Sintra-Sado Coastal Zone Land Use Plan (POOC)	RCM_86_2003_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2003	Despacho conjunto	Despacho conjunto n.º 329/2003	A project team is set up for the technical accompaniment of FINISTERRA Programme interventions	DC_329_2003_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2003	Resolução da Assembleia da República	Resolução da Assembleia da República n.º 11/2003	Approves, for ratification, the Convention on Access to Information, Public Participation in Decision-making and Access to Justice in Environmental Matters, signed in Aarhus, Denmark, on 25 June 1998	RAR_11_2003_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2003	Despacho	Despacho n.º 3337/2003 (2.ª Série)	Establishes the composition of the National Commission for the National Ecological Reserve, in representation of the Ministry of Cities, Land Use Planning and the Environment	Desp_3337_2003_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2003	Portaria	Portaria n.º 728/2003	Alters prices the Institute for Nature Conservation and Biodiversity should charge with the ambit of the Convention International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora	P_728_2003_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2003	Portaria	Portaria n.º 1354/2003	Prohibits the capture and trade of some polychaete species (<i>Marphysa sanguinea</i> , <i>Diopatra neapolitana</i> and <i>Nereis diversicolor</i>) in interior non-maritime waters under the jurisdiction of the Setúbal Port Authorities	P_1354_2003_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2003	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 17/2003	Alters the Regulatory Decree No. 18/99, which regulates environmental edutainment, combining education with entertainment and fun activities, environmental information and nature sports in protected areas, as well as licensing project initiatives and activities, services and facilities for environmental edutainment	DR_17_2003_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2004	Despacho Normativo	Despacho Normativo n.º 1/2004	Determines the composition of the National Commission for the National Ecological Reserve	DN_1_2004_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf

2004	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 1-A/2004	Approves the revision of the Sintra-Cascais Natural Park Land Use Plan	RCM_1-A_2004_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2004	Resolução da Assembleia da República	Resolução da Assembleia da República 19/2004	The Assembly of the Republic recommends that the Government take several measures seen as important for the protection of a sustainable forest	RAR_19_2004_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2004	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 3/2004	Alters Regulatory Decree No. 9/2000, which sets up the International Tagus Natural Park and alters the demarcation of this protected area	DR_3_2004_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2004	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 4/2004	Alters Regulatory Decree No. 10/2000, which sets up the Lagoa de Santo André and Lagoa da Sancha Nature Reserve and alters the demarcation of this protected area	DR_4_2004_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2004	Portaria	Portaria n.º 352/2004	Prohibits hunting in areas of non-regulated game hunting regime that are included in the Serra da Estrela Natural Park as a result of the previous summer's forest fires	P_352_2004_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2004	Decreto	Decreto n.º 7/2004	Approves the Cartagena Protocol on Biosafety to the Convention on Biodiversity, signed in Nairobi on 24 May 2000	D_7_2004_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2004	Despacho	Despacho n.º 7934/2004 (Série II)	On alterations to the demarcation of the National Ecological Reserve	Desp_7934_2004_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2004	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 33/2004	Determines the elaboration on the International Tagus Natural Park Land Use Plan and sets up its respective mixed coordinating commission	RCM_33_2004_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2004	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 56/2004	Determines the elaboration of the Albufeira do Azibo Protected Landscape Land Use Plan and sets up its respective mixed coordinating commission	RCM_56_2004_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2004	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 75/2004	Approves the Paúl de Arzila Nature Reserve Land Use Plan	RCM_75_2004_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2004	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 20/2004	Establishes the reclassification of the Serra de São Mamede Natural Park, maintaining its previous statute but redefining its demarcation	DR_20_2004_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2004	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 64/2004	Establishes the general application rules of the Rural Development Plan (RURIS), introducing some changes on the management of the aid regime	DL_64_2004_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2004	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 155/2004	Alters Decree-Law No. 169/2001, allowing the extraction of cork on holm oak trees affected by fires	DL_155_2004_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf

2004	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 156/2004	Establishes measures and actions to take within the ambit of the National System of Forest Protection and Fire Prevention	DL_156_2004_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2004	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 24/2004	Alters the demarcation of the Dunas de São Jacinto Nature Reserve as defined in Regulatory Decree No. 46/97	DR_24_2004_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2004	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 135/2004	Alters the demarcation of the Serra de Gardunha site (PTCON0028) on the national sites list	RCM_135_2004_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2004	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 180/2004	Approves strategic objectives for the National Strategy for the Environment and Sustainable Development (ENDS) 2005-2015, and defines the process for the elaboration of the final version	RCM_180_2004_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal
2004	Despacho	Despacho n.º 22641/2004 (Série II)	Approves regulations for the application of the funding regime in Measure 1.1. «Conservation and Enhancement of Natural Heritage» integrated in Priority I of the Environment Programme	Desp_22641_2004_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2004	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 202/2004	Establishes the legal and regulatory framework for sustainable hunting (regulating Law 173/99)	DL_202_2004_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2004	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 217-A/2004	Extends the duration for the elaboration of land use planning of protected areas established in Decree-Law No. 204/2002	DL_217-A_2004_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2004	Despacho	Despacho n.º 24999/2004 (Série II)	Determines inspection measures to take against infractions committed within the ambit of protected areas of national interested	Desp_24999_2004_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2005	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 49/2005	Alters the drafting of several articles in Decree-Law No. 140/99, which transposes the Birds Directive and the Habitats Directive	DL_49_2005_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2005	Portaria	Portaria n.º 164/2005	Sets the rates charged by the Nature Conservation Institute for issuing and renewing licenses	P_164_2005_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2005	Portaria	Portaria n.º 176/2005	Approves regulations for the application of zonal programmes within the ambit of agri-environment measures intervention (RURIS)	P_176_2005_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2005	Declaração de Rectificação	Declaração de Rectificação n.º 12/2005	Makes known that Ordinance (<i>Portaria</i>) No. 164/2005 was ratified and sets the rates charged by the Nature Conservation Institute	DRec_12_2005_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2005	Portaria	Portaria n.º 244/2005	Alters Ordinance (<i>Portaria</i>) No. 1102-F/2000, which approves the regulations for trawl net fishing	P_244_2005_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf

2005	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 77/2005	Approves Serra de São Mamede Natural Park land use plan	RCM_77_2005_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2005	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 2/2005	Alters the demarcation of Paúl do Boquilobo Nature Reserve, defined under the terms the Regulatory Decree No. 49/97	DR_2_2005_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2005	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 80/2005	Approves Serra de Malcata Nature Reserve land use plan	RCM_80_2005_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2005	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 103/2005	Approves the Vilamoura -Vila Real de Santo António Coastal Zone Land Use Plan (POOC)	RCM_103_2005_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2005	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 112/2005	Defines procedures for the elaboration of the National Strategy for Sustainable Development	RCM_112_2005_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2005	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 117/2005	New alteration of Decree-Law No. 19/93, which defines norms relating to the National Protected Areas network	DL_117_2005_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2005	Decreto Regulamentar	Decreto Regulamentar n.º 6/2005	Reclassifies the Esposende Coast Protected Landscape Area and alters the demarcation defined by Decree-Law No. 357/87 to now also include an adjoining marine area and be designated as the North Coast Natural Park	DR_6_2005_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2005	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 120/2005	Approves the Douro International Natural Park land use plan	RCM_120_2005_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2005	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 141/2005	Approves the Arrábida Natural Park land use plan; enlarges demarcation of this protected area to include a larger Marine Reserve area	RCM_141_2005_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2005	Despacho	Despacho n.º 24753/2005 (Série II)	Preservation of biological resources, values and processes of the National Ecological Reserve	Desp_24753_2005_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2005	Decreto-Lei	Decreto-Lei n.º 201/2005	Alteration of Decreto-Lei n.º 202/2004, which regulates Lei n.º 173/99 (General Framework Hunting Law)	DL_201_2005_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf
2005	Portaria	Portaria n.º 503/2005	Alters several articles of Portaria n.º 176/2005 (that sets regulations for the application of zonal programmes within the ambit of agri-environment measures intervention (RURIS))	P_503_2005_NATURE CONSERVATION_Portugal.pdf

BIBLIOGRAPHIC REFERENCES

AMARAL, Diogo Freitas do; ALMEIDA, Marta Tavares de (Coords.) (1994) *Direito do Ambiente*, Oeiras: Instituto Nacional de Administração.

CAMPOS, Rui Falcão de (1987) *Legislação portuguesa em vigor sobre protecção do ambiente e dos recursos naturais (actualizada a 30-06-1986)*, Lisboa: Secretaria de Estado do Ambiente e dos Recursos Naturais.

CENTRO DE ESTUDOS AMBIENTAIS E DE DEFESA DO CONSUMIDOR DO MINISTÉRIO DA JUSTIÇA – CENTRO DE ESTUDOS JUDICIÁRIOS (1994) *Direito do Ambiente* (8 tomos), Lisboa: CEJ.

CONDESSO, Fernando dos Reis (2001) *Direito do Ambiente*, Coimbra: Almedina.

MARTINS, Soveral (1988) *Legislação Anotada sobre Ambiente e Associações de Defesa*, Coimbra: Fora do Texto.

ROCHA, Isabel; VIEIRA, Duarte Filipe (1997) *Ar: Legislação, Contencioso Contra-Ordenacional, Jurisprudência*, Porto: Porto Editora.

SCHMIDT, Luísa (1999) *Portugal Ambiental: Casos & Causas*, Oeiras: Celta Editora.

SILVA, Vasco Pereira da (2006) *Ensinar Verde a Direito: Estudo de Metodologia do Ensino do Direito do Ambiente (em “Ambiente de Bolonha”)*, Coimbra: Almedina.

INTERNET SITES

Agência Portuguesa do Ambiente (APA) – Base de dados de legislação ambiental
<http://siddamb.apambiente.pt/>¹

Conselho Nacional do Ambiente e do Desenvolvimento Sustentável (CNADS)
<http://www.cnads.pt/>

Diário da República Electrónico²
www.dre.pt

Instituto da Conservação da Natureza e da Biodiversidade (ICNB)
<http://portal.icnb.pt/ICNPortal/vPT2007/>

Instituto Regulador de Águas e Resíduos (IRAR)
<http://www.irar.pt/>

Sistema Nacional de Informação de Recursos Hídricos (SNIRH)
http://snirh.pt/snirh.php?main_id=5&item=3.1&objlink=&objrede=

Estratégia Nacional para os Efluentes Agro-Pecuários e Agro-Industriais
<http://www.maotdr.gov.pt/Admin/Files/Documents/ENEAPAI.pdf>

Plano Estratégico de Abastecimento de Água e de Saneamento de Águas Residuais - PEAASAR 2007-2013
<http://www.maotdr.gov.pt/Admin/Files/Documents/PEAASAR.pdf>

Plano Nacional da Água – quadro legal e organização institucional e sociedade
http://www.inag.pt/inag2004/port/a_intervencao/planeamento/pna/pdf_pna_v1/v1_c2_t02.pdf

Constituição da República Portuguesa - Lei Constitucional nº 1/2005 de 12 de Agosto (sétima revisão constitucional) - Texto integral

¹ Where most legislative documents are available online.

² Also has most legislative documents available online.

EXPLAINING NOTE

Type of Legislation (Portuguese)	Short Reference	Type of Legislation (translated)
Acórdão do Tribunal Constitucional	ATC	Constitutional Court judgement
Aviso	A	Announcement
Declaração	Decl	Declaration, statement
Declaração de Rectificação	DRec	Statement of rectification
Decreto	D	Decree
Decreto do Governo	DG	Government Decree
Decreto-Lei	DL	Decree-Law
Decreto do Presidente da República	DPR	Presidential decree
Decreto Regulamentar	DR	Regulatory Decree, Implementing Decree
Despacho	Desp	Order
Despacho Conjunto	DC	Joint Order
Despacho Normativo	DN	Legislative Order
Despacho da Presidência do Conselho de Ministros	DPCM	Council of Ministers Order
Lei	L	Law, Act, Statute
Portaria	P	Ordinance, Order in Council
Resolução da Assembleia da República	RAR	Parliamentary resolution
Resolução do Conselho de Ministros	RCM	Council of Ministers Resolution